

Creative Arts Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. In Early 2024 we initiated a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure.

One of the proposed new activity areas is *Creative Arts*. We see an opportunity to facilitate and encourage exploration between and across stable, recognised datasets and collections to produce more profound and creative searches, across a broader range of disciplines and research paradigms. Starting with AustLit and AusStage, the lessons learned can extend to other datasets, creative art forms and researcher needs.

The ARDC is co-designing its new infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders to ensure that we create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

The ARDC conducted two co-design workshops in February 2024 to shape plans for this investment opportunity. These workshops were open to all, and were attended by a total of 128 participants from 54 organisations, including Australian and international universities, GLAM and arts organisations, research infrastructure providers, Creative Australia, and the Australian Academy of the Humanities. In Workshop 1 we refined our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and found out what outcomes participants hoped to see. In Workshop 2 we explored how the desired outcomes could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and discussed requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities.

The 2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap identified avenues to enhance the impact of HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research, proposing improvements in

coordinating research infrastructure to facilitate access to and analysis of physical and digital collections. These improvements involve leveraging tools like digitization, aggregation, and interpretation platforms.

Subsequently, the Australian Government Department of Education commissioned three studies to pinpoint investment-ready programs eligible for National Research Infrastructure funding. While not all recommendations from these studies received funding initially, the identified activities demonstrated a high level of readiness to engage with and benefit from the development of a [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

From 2022-2024 the ARDC-led HASS and Indigenous RDC has implemented a number of these activities, including:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities (IIRC) led by Dist Prof Marcia Langton, University of Melbourne
- Establishing the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA) led by Prof Michael Haugh, University of Queensland
- Developing Integrated Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences (IRISS) led by A/Prof Steven McEachern, Australian National University
- Creating the Trove Researcher Platform, which comprised Trove Enhancements (led by ANU) and the ARDC Community Data Lab (led by the ARDC)

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

Our commitment extends to supporting existing activities such as IIRC, LDA, the Community Data Lab, and Social Sciences while also considering the expansion of the RDC to include new activities for Creative Arts and Media(ted) Data. It has become evident that sustained investment is crucial to scale up these activities and provide coordinated digital research infrastructure meeting the needs of humanities, arts, social sciences, and Indigenous researchers.

Phase 2 aims to consolidate previous efforts, capitalise on synergies between existing and new projects, broaden partnerships and disciplinary coverage, and deepen engagement with the GLAM sector and Indigenous data governance.

In developing new activities, we have considered researcher needs gathered from consultations in 2021 and identified areas with active, coherent communities where research infrastructure can flourish. We have also looked at existing infrastructure that could be bolstered to transition into enduring national assets.

THE CREATIVE ARTS INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITY

The two largest, most sophisticated, mature, and best-known research infrastructure projects in the Australian cultural context are AustLit and AusStage. The two datasets form one of the Academy of Humanities' 50 Discoveries in 50 years. Together they hold data on nearly 2 million creative outputs. We see an opportunity to facilitate and encourage the exploration between and across these datasets and collections to produce more profound and creative searches, across a broader range of disciplines and research paradigms. These are the major research infrastructure resources for Australian cultural production and by providing a means for them to work together we feel we could facilitate a greater degree of documentation and cross-referencing, and significantly improved research capabilities for academics, arts industries, government, and the general public.

Previous attempts to link datasets in the humanities have stumbled over the absence of common metadata, and differing schema and ideological premises. We are hoping that by working with these two substantial and long-serving resources we can succeed in establishing a process that will facilitate the addition of other datasets, creative art forms and researcher needs as we proceed.

The proposed plan for Australian Creative Histories and Futures is being developed in collaboration with the University of New South Wales. Collaborating organisations include the University of Queensland (and AustLit), and Flinders University (and AusStage).

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

Problem Identification has taken place through extensive consultations and information gathering sessions, as described above. By tracking emerging gaps, opportunities, and sectoral trends, the ARDC has identified potential avenues for delivering benefits to the HASS and Indigenous research community. This strategic delineation of opportunities reflects the ARDC's commitment to addressing pertinent challenges and fostering innovation within the HASS and Indigenous research landscape.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the two open co-design workshops described below. Workshops were advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure

provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

WORKSHOP 1

The first co-design workshop was held virtually on 14 February 2024. It was attended by 98 participants from 46 organisations. Organisations represented included 27 Australian universities and an international university, as well as GLAM, research infrastructure, and arts organisations, Creative Australia, and the Australian Academy of the Humanities.

The aim of this first workshop was to refine our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and find out what outcomes participants want to achieve.

Professor Joanne Tompkins (University of Queensland), Professor Maggie Nolan (Auslit, University of Queensland) and Professor Chris Hay (AusStage, Flinders University) presented on the challenge, which they summarised with the following problem statement:

“Australian culture is extensive, dynamic and ever-evolving in whatever form it takes: theatre and performance, writing, art, design, music, or any other media. As such, it is difficult to document culture and preserve it for both research and for generating future creative developments.

Art is often made through broad networks: the interactions that shape Australian creative practice are multidisciplinary. We need to access our cultural history and heritage—as well as our cultural futures—through mechanisms that facilitate flow within and between forms and over time.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

- What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?
 - Disconnection between existing creative arts databases
 - Working across genre/form/modality is difficult
 - Access can be difficult - financial, disability, ease of use
 - Gaps in existing data and documentation
 - Diverse identities are not always represented
 - Disconnect between data/documentation and policy/decision-making
 - Sustainability of existing resources and infrastructure
 - Need for greater capability, skills and guidance
 - Need for storage of creative works and associated materials
 - Important to consider what media are to be included
 - Particular issues of copyright, IP and privacy
 - Links and relationships to be tracked are complex
 - Creative arts information crosses national boundaries
 - There have been past efforts in this space - important to learn from them
- Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)
 - Researchers
 - Creative practitioners
 - People of diverse and marginalised identities
 - Policy-makers
 - Students
 - The public
- What limitations are created by this challenge?
 - Research is limited by incomplete and disconnected information
 - Lack of access to good digitised copies of original works

- Data owners/custodians are often under-resourced to manage data
- Risks to sustainability of data collections and infrastructure
- There are blocks to data access for some users (financial, disability)
- Managing copyright and IP is complex
- What could we achieve by addressing it?
 - More deeply understand the creative arts
 - Increase access to creative arts data
 - Create richer data
 - Demonstrate the value of the creative arts
 - Create more sustainable infrastructure
 - Increase the user base for this data
 - Inspire new creative works
- Who could benefit?
 - Researchers
 - Creative practitioners
 - Policy makers
 - Students
 - GLAM and cultural institutions
 - Industry organisations
 - Curators
 - The public

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

- What outcomes would be beneficial?
 - Enable research across genres/forms/modalities
 - Trace artistic careers across modalities
 - Connect databases
 - Standardise data formats and metadata

- Make use of persistent identifiers
- Link to existing archives
- Improve search, visualisation and export of data
- Make data more accessible
- Identify gaps in coverage
- Represent diverse identities
- Enable research to track effects of funding, grants and policy
- Enable longitudinal research
- Increase awareness of data collections
- Ensure data is accessible to diverse audiences
- Allow data to be used for education
- Increase visibility and awareness of the arts
- Demonstrate the impact of the arts
- Inform future policy
- Support archive/digitisation of artistic works and related materials
- Provide training and increase technical capability
- Allow direct contributions to/editing of records
- Involve creative practitioners
- Support sustainability of the infrastructure
- What existing infrastructure/activities could we build on?
 - Participants gave an extensive list of existing platforms, organisations and initiatives that could be leveraged - see Appendix 1

Activity 3: Roles and partners

- What other kinds of partners need to be involved?
 - Creative practitioners
 - Arts organisations
 - GLAM organisations

- Industry associations and peak bodies
- Festivals
- Magazines and journals
- Government
- Indigenous communities and custodians
- Remote and regional stakeholders
- What other expertise/resources would benefit the project?
 - Expertise in Indigenous data governance
 - Expertise in disability and access
 - Technical expertise
- Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?
 - Groups working with disability and access and individuals with lived experience
 - Students and early career researchers
 - Creative practitioners
 - Archives and archivists

WORKSHOP 2

The second co-design workshop was held virtually on 27 February 2024. It was attended by 72 participants from 35 organisations. Organisations represented included 19 Australian universities and an international university, as well as GLAM, research infrastructure, and arts organisations, Creative Australia, and the Australian Academy of the Humanities.

The aim of this workshop was to explore how the desired outcomes identified by participants in Workshop 1 could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and understand requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

Staff from the ARDC reported back on the key findings from Workshop 1. Based on the responses to the Workshop 1 question “What outcomes would be beneficial”, we drew out four high-level outcome themes:

- "Provide connected and coherent interfaces to data", based on responses about connecting databases, using standardised formats, metadata and persistent identifiers, linking to archives,

improving ability to search, visualise and export data, making data more accessible, and enabling cross-modality research and the tracing of artistic careers across modalities.

- "Identify and fill gaps in the data", based on responses about identifying gaps in coverage; representing diverse identities, and enabling research that tracks the effects of funding, grants and policy, and research that looks at change and connections over time.
- "Build community engagement and human capability", based on responses about a need for training and capability raising, direct contributions to/editing of records, the involvement of creative practitioners, and a need for sustainability of infrastructure.
- "Enable outcomes and benefits beyond research", based on responses about a need for awareness of these data collections, their accessibility to diverse audiences and their use in education; increasing visibility and awareness of the arts; demonstrating the impact of the arts; informing future policy; and supporting the archive/digitisation of works and related materials.

We addressed each of these four outcome themes in turn. For each theme, Professor Maggie Nolan (AustLit, University of Queensland), Dr Caroline Wake (University of New South Wales), Professor Chris Hay (AusStage, Flinders University) and Rebecca Mostyn (Creative Australia) outlined a range of approaches and solutions that could be taken to achieve that outcome. In breakout groups, the workshop participants discussed those approaches, noting any requirements they would have for these approaches to be successful, and any practical considerations to be taken into account. Participants recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Common themes from the responses are recorded below, and full responses are attached in Appendix 2.

Provide connected and coherent interfaces to data

- Approach: Harmonise data models and schemas
 - Set up and document so that other databases can be brought into alignment later
 - Importance of community consultation and agreement
 - Don't lose the nuance of creative arts data when standardising
 - Consider CMS as an alternative approach
- Approach: Pilot an API(s)
 - Pay attention to user experience
 - Provide good documentation with examples
 - Community input and feedback to ensure API design meets needs of different users
- Approach: Align features across databases to give a more consistent user experience

- Consistency of experience less important than ease of use
- Language use can differ between art forms
- Quality metadata is essential
- Review the accessibility and inclusivity of features before aligning
- Approach: Investigate sustainability of the databases and asymmetry of access
 - Support for an open access model as the ideal
 - Use of volunteer data entry - but note this may not be sustainable
 - Need for long-term support and funding

Identify and fill gaps in the data

- Approach: Implement Indigenous Data Sovereignty and governance strategies
 - Build on existing work (e.g. BlackWords)
 - Resource Indigenous entities, projects and practitioners to engage
 - Use accessible, plain English language
 - Allow for the time it takes to connect with the correct people
- Approach: Consult with researchers, peak bodies, and communities to develop human-rights based approach to new ontologies and vocabularies
 - Ensure equal representation across artforms - don't bias to the dominant forms
 - Create an ethnic and gender identity taskforce
 - Need to revisit vocabularies as they change over time
 - Consider how to take into account sociocultural and sociopolitical considerations of terms used
- Approach: Pilot these ontologies via community co-design and targeted data entry efforts
 - Targeted data entry can be effective
 - Allow identification of gaps while maintaining data integrity
- Approach: Longer term: collect born-digital data by developing automated data ingestion/spidering options to gather data, de-duplicate it, and synthesise new records
 - Managing the tension between automated data ingestion and privacy, copyright and IP

Build community engagement and human capability

- Approach: Design and deliver a series of workshops and resources for researchers as well as for artists, authors and citizen scientists
 - Target workshops to a range of audiences, making use of existing events
 - Increase awareness of databases across non-researcher audiences
 - Work with educators of school students
- Approach: Develop capacity to annotate records
 - Annotation allows data to be enriched, but requires good moderation - how will this be supported?
 - Note the difference between annotation and altering the records themselves - the latter should be restricted (but with a request-change feature)
- Approach: Longer term: curate opportunities for creative uses of creative data through artists-in-residence for both databases
 - This could increase awareness of the data and highlight the importance of data integrity
 - Strong support for artists in residence
 - Other residencies - researcher-in-residence?
 - Student internships
- Approach: Longer term: cloud hosting solutions could also expand what is archived about arts practices
 - Sovereignty and security questions related to cloud hosting
 - Consider environmental sustainability
 - Expand with purpose - set sensible limits on what can/should be included

Enable outcomes and benefits beyond research

- Approach: Policy advice, advocacy, submission-making - expand how databases are used to impact future policy
 - Data would be valuable for industry advocacy
 - Map data to key portfolio areas
 - Increase accessibility of state and federal arts agency data - useful for peak bodies in informing policy

- Approach: Develop common data sources for the State of Culture report
 - Ensure representativeness of the data sources
- Approach: Evaluation of funding activities - longer-term tracking of impacts, career trajectories, sector change
 - Creative practitioners value the ability to record their careers in AusLit and AusStage
 - How do we measure the (non-financial) impact of creative work?
 - Concern about impact measures being used as metrics of “success” for funding recipients
- Actively connect artists, art organisations, curators etc with data to enable non-research outcomes
 - Note that the distinction between research and creative practice is not clear-cut - creative works can themselves be research outcomes

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close at the end of day, Friday 22 March. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2024.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line “Creative Arts”.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP 1 RESPONSES

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● there is a need to articulate Social Return on Investment in the arts - could this be factored in? ● Build in some information about policy/investment as a framework as well ● documentation of artistic practice is disconnected from policy, investment and other critical data ● Creating better networks and connectivity between databases. Also, access to some databases is a problem? ● One point to challenge with the problem statement concerns 'art is made through broad networks'....this is not always the case. Networks can operate as a form of gatekeeping to restrict access....which makes data access all the more important. ● making sure that data/databases are accessible to users - i.e. researchers and cultural practitioners - with disabilities ● Maintaining open access, any infrastructure to maintain interoperability needs to be less complex and accessible. HuN uses vernacular vocabulary to define relations between entities ● Providing access to a range of stakeholders in ways that are meaningful to them. (+1) ● Are Austlit and Austage the most mature databases in the country? ● "Are Austlit and Austage the most mature databases in the country?" - there are some internal issues with some of the arcgives we would like to link with. Can we fix these? perhaps not. I know for eg that it costs over \$200- to just get staff at the Screen Archive to check if specific TV programs are held at all, and then probably more to make copies to access. It's a bit shocking but I understand they are cash strapped. But it's the pointy end of these sticks like this I myself am most concerned about

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One challenge will be to make tools that can create links between data sources and treat these annotations as works in their own right (without building HuNI again) ● "One challenge will be to make tools that can create links between data sources ..." -HuNI is a good concept - linking across datasets, but we could think of it as an early attempt. With a few adjustments in how it's implemented it could take off. In doing so need to acknowledge the origins of the idea in HuNI's creators. ● "One challenge will be to make tools that can create links between data sources ..." - "HuNI is a good concept ..." - Of course -- but HuNI created proxies of datasets which increased complexity, drastically reduced the scope of what could be linked and broke down over time. ● "One challenge will be to make tools that can create links between data sources ..." - "HuNI is a good concept ..." - "Of course -- but HuNI created proxies of datasets..." - Yes, that's the main problem that should and can be solved. And the ability to link to things not already in the designated collections. ● "One challenge will be to make tools that can create links between data sources ..." - "HuNI is a good concept ..." - "Of course -- but HuNI created proxies of datasets..." - "Yes, that's the main problem that should and can be solved..." - WHY even have designated collections? Linked data allows annotation of anything with a stable URI ● Does the nature of the challenge also include reflecting on previous attempts to address and implement the challenge? What can be learned from the past? (+2) ● How robust is the data for every time period, place, genre etc? What is missing or cannot be captured? What needs to be done? (+1) ● I don't see the statement as a problem. Rather, the statement seems to be describing something axiomatic to any database. I am confused as to what the problem is. ● really different taxonomies and definitions - with some problematic, colonial and ableist classifications ● To me the problem statement assumes that cultural heritage can be "accessed" and that the means by which this occurs wouldn't participate in shaping what those records are; it also downplays the

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>value of friction and difference by imaging "flow" in terms of invisible interfaces that reinforce the sense of access without interference.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the multidisciplinary example of Trent Dalton: cross media adaptations often from multinational conglomerates outside Australia ● Very large scale DBs and integrations sometimes hide marginal groups in the noise of Big Data. So there needs to be tools to build 'focuses' on particular topics within the big data. Example I remember is building a resource on early modern women's archive of early publications that either don't fit into the conventional form of a publication that is amenable to database structures, and also, focuses on women, usually not visible in early modern studies. But the point is this sort of thing would be tech that enables the curated linking needed, rather than be part of the problem. ● Why does Australian culture need to be understood as data? It is so much more than data in need of documenting? I fear there's an instrumentalist approach right here at the start that misunderstands or assumes... (+1) ● the research output is a node graph ● Do we also need to think/reach internationally as 'Australian culture' reaches. and starts, beyond Australia (+1) ● Suggest "it is imperative to document culture..." cf "it is difficult..." ● Who owns culture? ● visuals/visualisations? (+1) ● A huge number of disparate databases, including institutional repositories all over Australia and the world ● Re nature of the challenge, i'm hear with two hats on Performing Arts Heritage Network (and I don't think we even know how many performing arts collections there are) and Theatre Heritage Australia (which has a significant collection of digitised programs). In my own research i'm turning up a lot of data about one late 19th century actor and i'm grappling with how to document that. ● I don't understand the mechanism by which this project will "generate future creative developments": how does this statement view/frame creative practice? (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● qualitative data that is more than or other than economic needs thinking through more deeply: what is value? what is valuable? ● need clear ethical frameworks and guidelines on data mgmt and access. these also need to be kept up to date with changing landscape with AI etc ● scope-Australia good; trans-Tasman better; Pasifika as well? (+1) ● how to reflect size of datasources? ● How will the project build capability across the creative sector to build that shared understanding - particularly for organisations and artists whose data is being used? ● Also, how will the project build capability for wider datasets to connect in that may not be part of the initial focus of the data ● HOw to build capabilities and transferable skills in a meaningful way build shared understanding especially in terms of creating safe spaces for working with sensitive data ● the problem statement, albeit focused on cultural data and content is indistinguishable from problem statements in public sector consultations for sector wide adoption of a standard CMS framework, ● we need better ways to integrate research outputs with creative works in our systems ● The services we have heard about are mostly data ABOUT creative arts -- what plans are there to store records of actual WORKS (+2) ● Just to second the point that it would be great to store works as well as information about works (+1) ● Is the intention to ask artists to document inspirations/networks that inform cultural outputs? ● To be able to glean relations and connections between cultural data (objects) generated through research and lived-experiences, by researchers and interested publics ● the challenge is 'relationship graphing' ● Better linkages to the products of creative activity held in GLAM collections (+1) ● There are so many possible ways of linking across these sources of information - time, place, people, themes.... (+2)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Picking up on the phrase "art is often made through broad networks" – and feeding this across the subsequent columns ... how will the identification and acknowledgement of those networks be resourced? By research? By artists inputting information? by external commentary/record? ● a digital abstract might be ;incremental, cumulative, granular, persistent and collaborative semantic annotation and linking of heterogeneous content and data' ● “We need to access our cultural history and heritage—as well as our cultural futures—through mechanisms that facilitate flow within and between forms and over time” makes sense, sounds great, in terms of the way in which grassroots action often proceeds strategic and planned action from government or industry or other actors in attempting to use cultural practice to impact society in some way (in my work), and is often transdisciplinary (in my work), however unsure if all end users will be clear meaning “mechanism” “flow” here ● ensuring the framework reflects different artforms but still allows useful comparison / cross referencing. ● This statement captures the important temporal dimension of the problem, and I love the cross-arts focus ● I think you need to define terms: 'Australian culture' is too broad a framing. Better to define as 'cultural activity' or 'cultural form' or 'production' -- i.e. 'theatre', 'performance' Characterising the current state of play: With existing data infrastructure we can enumerate distinct/discrete cultural activities (effectively, one or two-dimensional effort) but not able to explore cumulative relationships (3D) that would allow deeper insights and applications of Australian culture in its complexity. (+1) ● I think the capacity to ask questions across disciplines is really exciting. I often employ research assistants to enrich my annotated bibliographies of various literary forms with ADB, ONDB, DAAO, links to facilitate rich cultural histories. Imagine if that was automatically built into the datasets we regularly use

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Some groups have been excluded from culture - their practices have not been well documented - this gap risks reinforcing historical inequities (+1) ● Legacy data is not reflective of contemporary identities, so we cannot get a picture of diversity (+1) ● "Legacy data is not reflective of contemporary identities, so we cannot get a picture of diversity" - Culture is an evolving concept. It would be good if the database allow for expansion of what we are referring to as 'culture' especially as creative arts practitioners aren't restricted to one creative arts practice and will often engage with emerging arts and forms of popular culture. Popular culture in particular can be highly reflective of evolving conceptions of national culture. ● how expansive is too expansive? One repository for all things? is this possible? Capturing process is vital. We need data subset that capture Queer; inclusive/disability led process ● inclusion and representation. who are included and represented in such statements and initiatives (from a cultural and sociological point of view)))? (+2) ● Disconnection. An inability to 'cross-walk' datasets and collections, for public benefit. ● ● Is the idea to create a single massive database or to create and develop links between existing databases (while potentially creating new ones as well to better serve areas not currently covered)? (+3) ● "Is the idea to create a single massive database or to create and develop links between existing databases...." - I think it's important to build on systems that already have great architecture - like Austlit - rather than trying to reinvent the wheel... (+1) ● We are keen to explore the opportunity to network and share indexing and fielding with other organisations that have the same aims of linking cultural material. How do we develop databases that actually speak to each other and are mutually interchangeable. ● There are large gaps in our cultural history in databases like Ausstage due to missing data - this could be filled in with improved access to copyrighted publications and newspapers. In terms of preservation of

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>historical data unfortunately we are constrained by lack of technology to preserve this data. It is important moving forwards we have the correct vision and methods for documenting and recording cultural events.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Current datasets do not capture or reflect the full picture so interconnections and critical inputs are missing from the story ● some forms have not been dwell documented ● "some forms have not been dwell documented" - Digital audio media - podcasts, audiobooks - is one example. Probably all digital media: e.g. games, mobile applications, webseries ... ● "some forms have not been dwell documented" - Performance poetry would fit in the "not well documented" category, I'd say. ● Suggest "and other media" cf "or any other media" ● Would suggest some rewording from "extensive, dynamic ..." to the end of that sentence to better embrace all extant artforms and emerging/not yet emerged artforms/practices as well ● Statement needs to include "film and television" (potentially after "theatre and performance" ● "Statement needs to include "film and television" (potentially after "theatre and performance"" - Agreed! Screen/audiovisual/digital media are really absent from this ● Need to incorporate digital and audiovisual media: film, tv, audiobooks, podcasting, video games, other digital/online creative arts - you can't take a wholistic approach to considering Australian culture without these ● Need to consider long term access - preservation of data for future researchers (+2) ● Sustainability is more important than connection ● The challenge statement should acknowledge the key challenge of sustaining/protecting existing data sets that were funded by research funding and have no ongoing funding for maintenance etc. (+1) ● "The challenge statement should acknowledge the key challenge of sustaining...." - it seems there are several challenges here. As a historian, Im esp. concerned with archiving itself --- capturing and preserving past & present. This seems a real weakness currently as

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>most digital archives are incomplete or highly selective (and neither AusStage nor AustLit are true archives). So Im looking for better interoperability b/w actual holders of archival material and the excellent referencing capacities of the two</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● some data is private / not able to go into the public domain ● "some data is private / not able to go into the public domain" - yes. copyright will be a massive challenge ● "some data is private / not able to go into the public domain" - Not just copyright but ethics and participant agreements -- there is work under way on this in the Language Data Commons and IDN strands And ICIP ● Copyright, IP ● a platform to manage copyright permissions would be an incredible tool for the public gallery sector! ● Dialogue and guidance on how data is classified, and how we deal with legacy systemic inequities ● Not clear copyright policies. Vague metrics for ● What about intersections with international practitioners? How can these be documented, since connections are not only within Australia? (+2) ● Putting boundaries around the concept of 'Australian culture' in a globally linked world is problematic. ● Just seconding the comment about the need to consider intersections with international practitioners/cultural objects. Cultural practice is not just "australian" (increasingly so) ● How does the problem statement think through Australian 'culture' beyond national 'borders'? (+1) ● Is this also for global researchers to be able to discover Australian arts practitioners? The focus on access to our cultural heritage is so important, but does it exclude others who are not "us"? Or is better global visibility and connectedness perhaps a side- benefit of making this accessible to ourselves first? ● "Multidisciplinary" probably needs expansion in some way to include multicultural international, multi linguistic... ● I'm concerned that people are using AusStage and Trove (I'm less concerned about AustLit) to make analytical conclusions assuming the

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>data is substantially complete. As we discussed re performances of Patrick White plays in Brisbane/Queensland, AusStage says zero only because no-one has searched the relevant years yet.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Re Trove, I'm not sure if I've mentioned that I'm writing a biography of the vaudeville singer Joy Nichols jointly with Joy's daughter Roberta Hamond, who has inherited her press cuttings books. As well as the poor scanning accuracy of Trove documents which means that many items are missed in key word searches, there are many periodicals that aren't in their database (Radio Pictorial of Australia and People are notable omissions for my purposes - Roberta's sending me dozens of items from such sources which sometimes turn the story upside down). Meshing databases could directly magnify the errors and indirectly conceal the absences.
<p>Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Impacts anyone working on creating or commissioning new work, as well as researchers, and potentially audiences as well ● marginalised groups; accessibility concerns; process driven art making; cross genre/interdisciplinary transdisciplinary' ● researchers, policy makers, funding agencies, content creators, students, need to be able to see how the practices of the past have evolved, what impact positive or negative / expected or unexpected they have had, to be able to tell their stories/histories, show their achievements, strategise for futures ● There are access issues for regional artists as they generally don't have access to networks or ways of documenting work. If this project could allow better connectivity to regional archives that would be amazing. We have 2 at UNE that I would love to include as part of the project. We are currently developing the Stage on Screen archive for digital access through the UNE library. The Campbell Howard archive needs digitisation first. (+5) ● "There are access issues for regional artists as they generally don't have access to networks or ways of documenting work." - There's been something of a step towards this in AustLit's Australian Drama Archive (which is mostly Euncie Hanger Collection), but would love to see the Campbell Howard collection digitised and available!

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need to consider accessibility from a diverse user group including artists with disabilities ● current researchers and practitioners, and future generations ● isn't the funding for research infrastructure? Shouldn't it be supporting researchers to use databases rather than creative practitioners (noting that there are cases where researchers are creative practitioners or creative practice is research practice) ● Cultural Researchers/CI researchers and practitioners ● This might not only be research tools, but the tools may be an artistic medium. Eg: using web maps to write a fiction; using interactive network visualisations between data sets on artists to create a critical intervention displayed in a gallery, etc. So artists/creatives as well as researchers. ● This will be so important for artists to be able to discover like-minded people across the spectrum of different arts. This discoverability aspect will be amazing to support inter-arts activity. (+1) ● Creative practitioners. If we want to generate future creative development, we need to consider what kind of information they need (quite diff from what academic researchers might need) ● Researchers, teachers, students general public who are curious about "culture". Does there need to be a sense of "play" included? (+1) ● This challenge affects Australia as a whole, but many may not be aware that they are affected in the first place. ● Anyone who would like to access data about 'Aust culture', especially those who don't have bespoke skills aligned with specific databases ● who or what is this for who benefits ● public galleries - there are over 400 across Australia and the majority will have their own collection databases using an array of collection databases. (+2) ● Our future selves? ● Intellectual property holders ● Networks include arts industry and adjacent industries: not just arts bodies etc, e.g. recording companies, publishers, etc. The marketplace is a consideration/potential source of partners. (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I think it'll be very important to engage school kids at both primary and secondary levels, but their needs may be very different from older users'. Will reading-age-related accessibility be facilitated by the platform? ● Students at all levels - undergrad, honours, postgrad. ● Decision-makers, ie, govt agencies shaping the future of the sector ● Policy makers ● It is not hard to imagine that the nature of this enterprise might be perceived as alienating by some marginal groups and this could very easily create a feedback loop. Start out already on the margin, feel alienated, don't engage, end up more marginalised. ● migrants, who contribute not only to the economy but also creative, cultural, and social landscape of Australia ● Anyone interested in biographical research and writing.
<p>What limitations are created by this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● gaining non-digitised archival data from time and resource poor arts organisations ● Is there any support available for archives that are not in digital form yet? ● Non-text, digitally recorded performance/installations are hard to meaningful capture for reuse ● "Non-text, digitally recorded performance/installations are hard to meaningfully capture for reuse" - just converting for e.g. VHS to digital is much harder than most people think, and then there is the issue where the file will live (and if that location is secure into the future). At the moment Australia is failing badly at this ● will emphasis on 'multi-disciplinary' mean less emphasis on individual arts forms? (+2) ● Is there risk that a focus on interoperability will diminish the expanse of the complexity of datasets for individual arts forms? ● Cultural transmission – at the moment, our network analyses hits impenetrable data walls when we move beyond live or streamed performance. Most obvious blocks are following associations of artists from live performance to screen performance or gaming.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● We are only ever getting part of the story. As is reflected in the new financial data for AusStage, there are many aspects of researching the creative arts that extend far beyond just the works themselves. ● AusStage needs some modernization work before we can join Auslit in some version of a shared data warehouse.. the ideal configuration for this warehouse would allow each of our platforms to still function as an autonomous transactional system, but where we can share reporting and analysing systems. And this warehouse model needs to be designed to host other creative arts datasets. ● How well can AustLit and AusStage have a dialogue? Data models are similar, but are there missing links? ● The rights of intellectual property holders need to be respected: Australian authors, for example, need to be consulted on what you mean by 'data' ● We're finding copyright challenges very complex for the university archives - but a new 'can do' library contact is making a major difference. (+1) ● including visual art images that are subject to copyright. ● Access, alongside security and stability of content ● issues of access, management and future proofing are key ● BlackWords is an amazing piece of infrastructure, not being open access (ie being subscription only) is a particular problem. Similar point was made above. It limits access to the resource and also opportunity for interaction with the resource and community-driven ideas about improvements. ● How might people of other linguistic backgrounds with lower proficiency in English be engaged in and able to access material on this platform? Will multilingual metadata be used at all? Will it be possible for them to read material in other languages? What about translations of Australian literary works in other languages? Will these be represented in the platform (together with their translators)? ● Technological and financial limitations?(+1) ● Individuals who possess personal records and archives may not have the platforms nor institutional resources to house and upload their

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>content. This is especially true of AusStage which links to externally-held sources.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The obvious significant limitations to obtaining this data are the resources necessary to collate and upload it. (+1) ● Supporting compatible data development for under-resourced orgs / artists / individuals on an ongoing basis ● the content creators who produced the data/were the subject of the data produced have not always had the time, money, capacity, or permission to document their history in their own terms, finding it, collating it, collaborating to identify the pieces that ‘evidence’ community memory of history, and best way to share, is challenge for this reason ● Sustainability ● How would these databases/archives be maintained and updated? Would organisations need to submit information to admins or would there be a degree of Wikipedia-style data entry/editing possible? ● Websites cant be set up and left. They need ongoing maintenance ● sustainability and keeping information up-to-date with the rate of change occurring ● Interface? How can all the data be consumed/used/repurposed by the user? Visualisation? ● How do people like us - researchers, artists and so on -interact with the technical people who will have a big role in implementing a shared system?" - Finding and utilising "purple people" = a growing cohort of the people in the middle of tech+HASS who can help translate both ways :) ● How do people like us - researchers, artists and so on -interact with the technical people who will have a big role in implementing a shared system? We have developed our own system at the Australian Dictionary of Biography which has cost us heaps and which we started from scratch. Sharing experience seems to be fundamental. (+2) ● careful engagement with Indigenous Elders and close collaboration with Indigenous communities is essential for success and meaningful capture, storage and access (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It seems important to find ways to link directly to works (where possible) and to find ways to work with existing archives (eg literary magazines, art galleries, theatres, publishers) so that the databases can include more than just records. That way researchers can potentially get access to a much greater depth of information. (+1) ● still so many different approaches to each of these topics/matters ● "How would these databases/archives be maintained and updated? Would organisations need to submit information to admins or would there be a degree of Wikipedia-style data entry/editing possible?" - i think we would have to calve that off from main pages; we need only authorised editing; managing databases is VERY hard; I know one major national database filled by unpaid volunteers for many years and that one had lots of repetition, mistakes, ommissions, and sources often not give ● Is there any sense of broader impacts and opportunities to come out of this work, including eg. audience cultivation for the arts? ● To have a separate infrastructure to build relations and connections between cultural data entities, there is a need for a convenient platform for managed data structuring, for researchers and publics (+1) ● Who is authorised to speak and contribute and accepting different, diverse, and competing knowledge systems and views of the world (+1) ● Agree re. competing knowledge systems (another note here) The inclusiveness of the metadata categories will be critical for addressing this. ● Support for researchers/end users to make the most of the data – export, visualisations, analysis etc ● One state library ensures subscription access to its state-wide network of public libraries, training is an issue for more effective take-up and use in communities.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What could we achieve by addressing it?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● much better cross-genre understanding ● A better understanding of where we are, and where we're heading, and hopefully, why we should care ● Greater understanding of the dynamic forces intrinsic to 'culture' and what fosters the development of different aspects of creative development ● An understanding of inspirations and conversations between different pieces and different artworks ● An important source of context in terms of understanding how works have been inspired/built in the past and how these feed into new works for the future ● Greater awareness of existing and developing creative practices and connections. ● Understanding culture in terms of time and space. (+2) ● increased representation of migrants who have creative and cultural contributions to Australia despite visa status ● information about practices and processes that can inspire future creative work ● Yes, creative re-use is an interesting idea I think. Copyright issues of course to consider ● Sustainability of cultural datasets - resourcing Australia's literary heritage/future (+1) ● Longer lasting artefact ● i would put it differently. it is not only that research needs money. rather simply keeping something needs money. you cant build a box and leave it. it falls apart ● Better impact ● Tech language - how do we speak the same one - metadata eg dublin core - we are at the beginning & don't want to go down the wrong path - how to keep interoperable as a broad direction ● I am aware that the search language can limit what is found in a database. The research question that is more qualitative can often only start from databases. How can we correlate the perspectives of the art work?

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● First: do we want it addressed in this way? Is data capture and storage and 'sale' in digitised form really genuinely protective of creatives and local publishers/arts organisation in a digital and AI era? ● greater visibility & buy in from the general public for HASS research ● Reducing duplication of effort, complexity of navigating multiple data sources (+1) ● identifying gaps; highlighting under-served areas that need investment ● unequal power relationships between the Arts forms and economic -socialcapital ● Building research based links and connections between cultural collections will allow contestability and the acceptance of difference (race, culture, politics, epistemologies) (+1) ● cross fertilisation with other disciplines (+1) ● I'd really like archiving itself improved. As an eg, finding reviews of productions or anything else is nearly impossible now because most of the digital databases for newspapers do not in fact include this material at all (Informit, most of the newspaper databases, etc). This means at this time if you want to get a sense of what was in the papers even in the early 2000s, you must go to a holding library and sometimes even scroll at random through microfilm. That's pretty disappointing. Could we maybe stop offshoring these databases a bit more and extend Informit? ● Sharing of group biographical information and network analysis. The ADB refers only to people who have died whereas Austlit and Austage incorporate contemporary figures. This promises a greater but perhaps even more vibrant coverage than we have at present. ● We could achieve an extraordinary resource that reflects and supports the full dynamism of Australian arts and culture ● What could we achieve by addressing it? – make sure communities (cultural, artistic, etc.) have access to their history, their story, and capacity to use the learnings to make case for particular paths forward in policy, funding, infrastructure, cultural investment ● End Users, usages, impact - open access vs monetisation/subscription models per above, teaching, research, policy, etc

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It would be wonderful to be able to link directly to works from archives/databases as this could greatly enrich awareness of the richness and depth of existing archives held by other orgs while also making the information much more accessible to researchers ● Broader access, better connectivity ● engaging new stakeholders in national research / national & cross artform approach to creative arts research ● Larger audience ● Impact data with geo-spatial parameters ● demonstrating connectedness, impact and value of the arts ● Being able to recognise the value of artistic practice
<p>Who could benefit from addressing this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enabling different access options depending on relationship to data could be a concern with Indigenous creative productions. ● "Enabling different access options depending on relationship to data could be a concern with Indigenous creative productions." - agreed. Protocols and frames are crucial as well as Indigenous governance and participation ● Enabling options for different access to data could be of interest for some Indigenous cultural and creative producers. Anything publicly available could have layers of development behind it that don't make it to the public version but that could be of dynamic interest to particular knowledge-holders. ● How can we best communicate best practice in terms of the data tech we're using. ● Historians ● international visibility ● Editors ● We need a Queer sub data set; a disability/inclusive data sub set; an institutional training data set. I would like process to be captured, especially for community engaged art making creative process not only end product ● Findable piece of art or artefact ● Support to small to medium orgs in better understanding data management and collection, maintenance etc.; support in holding data externally for preservation.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Australian cultural knowledge and productive recognition of different voices in our cultural heritage ● All those with an interest in Australian culture. researchers, students, general readers as well as cultural organisation (+1) ● The vast diversity of researchers and students as well as the general reading public who utilise our materials. Reducing isolation and duplication promises a more utilisable and valuable facility. ● English readers -- and readers of other languages? ● The beneficiaries are all Australians, as well as people elsewhere who want to understand Australians (+2) ● Is there public benefit? Good question! ● Audience (by creating curiosity loops that lead from one artform back to its inspirations or predecessors) ● benefit for all society ● Programmers and curators (festivals and exhibitions) ● curators developing exhibitions ● Australian publishers (or not) depending on how you approach intellectual copyright ● students, teachers, libraries, researchers, industry (+1) ● GLAM and Industry Partners (+1) ● researchers, policy makers, funding agencies, content creators, students ● government, other collecting agencies (+1) ● Model impact of policy decisions on sector (+1) ● Artists ● writers (or not, depending upon how you approach intellectual copyright) ● I would love to see benefits flow to amateur creative practitioners ● Creative writers: scholarship and reception of their work made visible to future readers/researchers ● research outputs and researchers (+1) ● creative practice researchers ● Researchers, not just in discovering evidence, but also seeing their place in it as researchers in traditions.

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What outcomes would be beneficial?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standard metadata description (+1) ● Stand off' annotation of collections. ● it would be beneficial to have broadly comparable details to help build consistency between data sets. ● "it would be beneficial to have broadly comparable details to help build consistency between data sets." - This is useful for new projects but tricky for existing ones ● Consistency across the records (in terms of data presentation/content etc) so that search results can be more easily compared and analysed ● Bust cultural mythologies about Australia; bring un-acknowledged voices, people, practices, strengths and failings to light. Test assumptions, advocacy assumptions about arts and culture in Australia by interrogating funding data alongside performance etc. Make a policy case for the underpinning role of arts and culture for living well. (+1) ● understanding the level of funding required to ensure the creative industries can thrive (ie the current underfunding of the sector). This relies on the social return on arts investment to be captured and reported on. (+3) ● Impact data that takes into account more than/other than standard economic factors (i.e. beyond audience numbers, book sales (+3) ● visibility, particularly for the community visibility of what is historically/at present not visible, not collected, not profiled, not celebrated, then beyond that the answers to the previous re using lessons from analysis of history to inform future strategy, policy, funding, infrastructure, etc., then additionally there is also the opportunity to look to specific training the data sets can support e.g. language learning for students in schools or cultural learning for students in schools and so forth ● Being able to track across modalities will help with policy ● Map impact of decision-makers on sector and therefore future model impact ● Getting culture recognised in the next SDGs (+2)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● creating databases that can produce/provide other layers of data to underpin subsequent policy decisions ● Advocacy and broad representation in the continued development of Federal Arts policy ● Ability to connect developments in practice with significant policy, sector development and related activity ● Connecting with the collections/ archives/datasets of journals and lit mags to increase access to content and to conversely improve search function and awareness of that cultural infrastructure. ● an inclusive, accessible, cross disciplinary archive of practice, process and 'product/event' ● Open Access online archive of filmed performances, interviews, documentaries etc - video database (+1) ● A mechanism to encourage visibility of the databases and easier/wider access (+1) ● "A mechanism to encourage visibility of the databases and easier/wider access" - Quality metadata will be imperative. ● open access and crowd sourcing of archival research, and a much more creative and collective efforts in interpretation of cultural collections and data based This relies on a management of gate-keeping tendencies by cultural institutions, and more creative data structuring ● Greater understanding, appreciation of Australian arts and creative culture and history along with greater accessibility to information ● greater public access and participation in cultural data, and the possibilities of interpretations and verifications based on humanities and creative research and lived-experience. ● Free access to Austlit (+8) ● Accessibility of data/interface/affordances ● The Gender Index' - data viz exploring gender in the oz publishing industry over time (+1) ● Usable timelines and maps (+1) ● Visualisations for results that indicate gaps in coverage. (+1) ● Generous interfaces. new ways of visualising data (+2)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It would be great to have access to other databases like Imdb (currently limited search function ability) in order to track the cultural influences of artists and playwrights between live performance and screen. ● Being able to search data pooled from both archives (AustLit and AusStage, plus any more that might get interpolated) to run more comprehensive search outcomes. eg about particular authors and their writing across mediums; about specific locations and the work being generated in it. ● Seamless discoverability and interoperability between contiguous databases - writing, production and consumption, format-agnostic (screen, print, stage, etc) ● Cross-pollination of databases to reveal inspiration and intersection between artists and outputs (+1) ● Integrating datasets/putting them into conversation could help identify gaps and biases in each. ● the linking of research that has been done into database so as to not repeat the work ● Mechanisms to allow the databases/archives of literary journals and other publications (digital and printed) to interact with AustLit (+4) ● Interface with other national databases; Australian writers and performers travelled widely and evidence is found "offshore" ● If not interoperable, then having the projects somehow reference to each other. Knowledge of the other databases is sometimes half the hurdle even if that data cannot be combined into the master projects e.g. AustLit (+2) ● explore particular topics, themes, time periods, moments across multiple databases for a fuller, more rounded picture of it ● enable cross-platform reporting from a common data model ● Beneficial outcomes for me as theatre historian would be coincidence of data currently on Th Aotearoa (currently underway with AusStage), as well as Aus Stage, AusLit, and also Clay Djubal's data - sorry Clay have forgotten link to this (nice to see you by the way). So that's really the infrastructure to build on - and then there's the data i'm gleaming from 46,000 newspaper records (Britain, America, NZ and Aus).

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● being able to cross-reference/work across Trove and any other cultural database would be immensely beneficial ● Understanding artists' development journeys through time better -- e.g. what were the milestones (in retrospect) and which of these were linked to funding that was received, enabling this? (+4) ● Something with an easy name and concept that funders will understand ● In terms of the Financial Field in Ausstage it would be beneficial to create partnerships with both government departments, private enterprise and practising artists to collect financial data. Often what is available is the last 2-3 years worth of reports by major companies online. Requesting data at a local government level I have also found there are barriers. We need to promote the benefits of collecting financial data for the arts sector as a whole in order to achieve this. ● Develop further the functionality of the financial field in Ausstage to provide common SQL requests when interrogating the financial data ● Longitudinal career analysis ● Following an individual's artistic expression over time ● An additional collection document from the group that would be good is all the existing data sets people here are aware of - we have some, but there's clearly people have others, to give a sense of scope of what is extant could be stabilised and supported, before getting to question of new - perhaps even things that could be salvaged/revived if projects were started but not funded and fell into disrepair ● see my notes to previous. Id like to see cross link between the actual housing institutions / archives and the databases increased (so links, not simply lists of sources to then look up). Id also like the actual archival potential of the two databases increased (so these websites as hosting archival material such as scans, docs, images, video). at the moment for AusStage for eg we have to put clips on Youtube or Vimeo. These are very unreliable holding systems which are liable to disappear in yrs to come ● Sustainability of data/resources/end user interface over time, maintenance ● Ensuring future-proofing of creative arts datasets

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Another reason to get serious about sustainable storage for nationally significant data resources. ● tracking of literary events - festivals, launches, readings etc - both contemporary and historical (+1) ● There are any number of digital projects in this space relating to Australian cultural heritage. E.g. ADB, Linked Archive, AusStage, Common Reader, the RED Australia branch, plus any number of small ones created by PhD students and other research projects that could benefit the broader researcher community ● STANDARDISATION OF INCOME FOR ARTISTS ESPECIALLY THOSE WHO REGULARLY PLAY IN ENTERTAINMENT VENUES ● sharing of reporting data - that we provide to state and federal arts agencies (+2) ● Opportunities to research and explore new areas of study as well as allowing for more serendipitous discovery of related information ● management of conflict of interest by a governance structure that includes a range of researchers, practitioners and projects ● Enhanced capacity to produce evidence-based research and therefore real-world impact ● Developing international links to maximise reach ● Automated data ingestion ● Audiobooks in AustLit (+2) ● Ability for direct contributions from research projects ● As an author and a researcher, I would like to be able to track influences and relationships between authors over time (and between different genres/creative arts) ● Cross-genre digital arts dataset would be really useful ● Better understanding and awareness of cross disciplinary influences and ● Being able to track not only the original works but also their adaptation (in all genres) (+1) ● A genuinely multidisciplinary approach to the creative arts that doesn't have theatre and performance standing in front of or in place of other artforms

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More knowledge of the existence of these projects as well as knowledge of how to use them effectively ● Guidance for working appropriately with identification & identities ● It would be great to be able to run the sorts of searches that it might technically be possible to do but which we don't know how to do as casual visitors/researchers: eg pull data about all of the plays being produced by a number of theatre companies in a particular year/season and who wrote/directed/performed in it to generate meaningful Australian content searches, etc. (+3) ● greater teaching tools--how to do things in both, and between both ● Greater engagement for teachers with work that underpins the pieces recognised as Australia's cultural output (book, play, poem, etc) ● To be able to trace more cohesive histories of institutions (+1) ● Large-scale longitudinal research (+1) ● Greater ability to link directly to works where possible (eg: AustLit being able to link directly to the digital versions of articles/publications where available) as as this would not only add greater depth to already rich and detailed records but would also offer researchers more direct access to more detailed information while also benefiting the organisations that published the works (+3) ● Connections with archival material eg NLA archives ● central record of where artists' papers are held in archives ● Writers/authors/creatives clearly consulted on permissions around who can collect, access and use their work on any new databases - where primary work is captured ● Digitised ephemera point made by someone else, YES. ● Another comment discussed the ability to provide a more comprehensive repository on works. The existing works section in Ausstage could be built further to accommodate this. ● Accessing / storing production ephemera (photographs, videos) from theatre companies or their equivalent ● I feel it will be important to allow artists to edit their own biographical information (including, e.g. pronouns) ● there is a danger in letting artists do their own entries since it assumes we can trust them, which is not always true. At the very least

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>they should be required to give sources. I am writing a book in which one artist has claimed authorship of their collaborators and if we let artists themselves do their pages this kind of thing is inevitable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● enable the right to be invisible? some information is negative as well as positive ● Creators front and centre in the framework development - make sure whatever is developed works with creators to understand what they do ● Anything which connects the infrastructure to the audiences for cultural outputs. ● We need a Queer sub data set; a disability/inclusive data sub set; an institutional training data set. I would like process to be captured, especially for community engaged art making creative process not only end product; we need to make economically viable for small organisations and institutions (+1) ● to 'decolonise' (generally speaking) archives and cultural collections (+4) ● Adaptations in Indigenous hands is a fascinating zone of Australian creative arts eg Leah Purcell Drover's Wife. Enabling pathways through data that illuminates these journeys and impacts would be great. ● visibility and recognition of diverse cultural contributions and activity / outside the 'canon' ● This likely depends on online organisations maintaining persistent links. So if they change their URL conventions, they should provide versioning information that explains how the old links map to the new links, otherwise all the spin offs that link this to that will be broken and can't easily be fixed. ● persistent links to records (and versions of records) for referencing ● Raising awareness of regional and remote creative ecologies ● Increase depth of knowledge across generations/expand historical context/perspective etc for new works ● Improved media coverage of creative arts is, I think, important -- getting research infrastructure into media mindsets could be a goal and outcome.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fuller Export functions that enable data analysis ● APIs to allow for the full ontologies / relations of data to be exported (+2) ● As my paper on echoic biography suggests, it may be necessary if the aim is to produce genuinely useful and comprehensive records, to start to hotlink to primary sources including out-of-copyright aural and both still and moving visual material. Part of the planning might need to consider how and where very large data sets can be funded, created and stored.
<p>What existing infrastructure/ activities could we build on?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The value of AusStage is that it is open access. The artist can check on a listing. ● We have a series of MOUs with cultural organisation.s there must be a better way to do it! (+1) ● Build in AI as it develops within the framework of privacy, security and copyright (+3) ● We would very much love the possibility of Pokemon Go for Australian stories: being able to read locally ina very very local sense. (+2) ● A better CoP community building amongst creatives and broader society ● i don't know: my view is we lack infrastructure and need more genuinely consultative work on the question of how to get there from here ● Protection of our IP and copyright being in a centrally controlled data base ● There is a need to review past successes and failures to achieve desired outcomes (+2) ● shared language & increased capability across arts sector (outside research institutions) to engage with and contribute to the data ● integrating a wide range of existing databases in anything other than a perfunctory manner may not be feasible. Might be better to develop, propagate and manage a distribution of mainstream open-source CMS framework and migrate databases to that framework with their own theming. (+2)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National digitisation program, sustainably funded (+1) ● Taking a 'sandpit' approach, convening 'play' groups could be valuable. ● Accessibility principles in all design is fundamental. ● reporting provided to State and federal arts agency (+1) ● "reporting provided to State and federal arts agency" - Definitely connect up with the work being achieved in the Improving Indigenous Research Capability Project and the Language Data Commons. So much Indigenous creative production connects with rich cultural assets -- there need to be designed connections in the research infrastructure consistent with IDG principles and values. ● Other HASSI data commons streams AND the Community Data Lab ● Existing institutional repositories (+1) ● State and federal funding bodies' archives - annual reports, commissioned reports, etc ● Citizen humanists (+1) ● Look at existing models for roll-out of interoperable web sites in the public sector ● Invest in and support a number of projects attempting to document and build databases of invisible cultural activity and contributions - disability arts, cultural diversity ● public gallery collection databases (over 400 galleries in Australia using up to 10 different CMS). ● NCRIS facilities ● Grass roots web-first movements and collections, like with fan fiction, vaporwave etc. ● Local art galleries and museums ● Existing digital archives held by lit mags etc. ● building on data that is housed in other repositories that interconnect with AustLit and AusStage (+2) ● Do not overlook partnerships and collaborations with small to medium orgs who hold data which might otherwise be lost or poorly protected / disseminated (+2) ● There is an existing connection between Austlit and the Australian Poetry Library (APL) in the form of links from AustLit's author pages to

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>those on APL. It would be good to renew these and expand them somehow—perhaps reverse-engineer the same links from APL back to AustLit, or otherwise? Though APL would need funding to implement such changes. It would also be good to see free access to AustLit. APL has free access. (+1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The ADB has put immense resources into building and developing and communicating data. It would be great not to redevelop the wheel but to draw on other organisational experience. ● https://www.americantheatrearchiveproject.org/ ● Wikidata -- already includes many crosslinks between these dbs (+1) ● TLCMap provides a model for layered interactive mapping ● National Libraries ● National Public Galleries Alliance benchmarking (+2) ● Archival collections of journals/magazines/newspapers etc as well as Trove (+1) ● <u>Also of interest might be this re. the ‘collections as data’ movement: https://openhumanitiesdata.metajnl.com/articles/10.5334/johd.124</u> ● PIDs services via ARDC ● GLAM institutions especially e.g. NFSA, VAC Museum and the like ● There is also Victorian Collections - a free, cloud based collection database developed by Creative Victoria and also being used in WA). ● cultural policy and research databases (eg APO) (+2) ● GLAM Workbench -- for accessing and using related material in GLAM collections (+1) ● Place-based repositories like the Cultural Atlas of Australia, the Dictionary of Sydney, etc ● I liked the reference to “networked practices” and wonder how HUNI (see above) could be networked with through this new investment and project opportunity. ● links with AIATSIS if we don't have these (+3) ● https://www.nzonscreen.com/ ● <u>Literary map of WA: https://www.lovetoreadlocal.org/</u> ● The Cultural Atlas of Australia for geovisualised mapping data. That resource is no longer being updated for new content. ● ArtsHub

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HuNI (Humanities Networked Infrastructure) is a knowledge graph with eighteen million nodes, drawn from thirty-three data sources including Trove and AustLit which reflect the perspectives of different disciplines across the humanities and creative arts. HuNI has been designed to support complexity, contestation, and connection, through user-generated links and collections of entities. Multiple interpretations of relationships – including conflicting ones – can be represented. ● Links with ASA and writers centres ● Copyright agencies collect valuable information about who has authored what works and (e.g. in the case of composer/writer collaborations, e.g. APRA AMCOS) what their contribution was to a particular outcome. (+1) ● https://www.nfsa.gov.au/ ● Collections of digitised ephemera in Trove -- includes many theatre posters, programs (+1) ● https://www.apraamcos.com.au/ ● Wikipedia, Wikidata and commons do loads with GLAM sector and would be great partners ● Trove!!! Moving data over from Trove into AusStage is laborious and unnecessary, given that the site links to Trove anyway! ● TLCMap (+2) ● "TLCMap" - ANd associate work such as GHAP ● A stronger relationship between Austli and the ASA and APA/SPN (Australian publishers assoc. and Small Press Network) (+1) ● Utilise Austlit's own comprehensive database as the backbone for data visualisations. (+4) ● "Utilise Austlit's own comprehensive database as the backbone for data visualisations." - As has been done in AustLit's Australian Writing and Rock Music dataset, which uses visualisations tied to dynamic data to showcase relationships. ● Digitised books and periodicals in Trove (currently about 20,000 books and 10,000 periodicals) (+1) ● It would be great to incorporate (and expand? restart?) oral histories like those collected by the NLA

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "It would be great to incorporate (and expand? restart?) oral histories like those collected by the NLA" - Prof Catherine Travis (ANU) of LDaCA is working on this ● HuNI - (Humanities Networked Infrastructure) is a knowledge graph with eighteen million nodes, drawn from thirty-three data sources which reflect the perspectives of different disciplines across the humanities and creative arts. HuNI has been designed to support complexity, contestation, and connection, through user-generated links and collections of entities.- ● "HuNI - (Humanities Networked Infrastructure) is a knowledge graph with eighteen million nodes" - Most of those data sources are inoperable - and there are only a handful of collections of links that have been created between them. Has HuNI EVER been used to do research that could not have been done without out it? (Citations plz) last time I looked these claims about contestation etc are over stated - it collected pairs of links that was all and most of the public data sets appear to be the output of workshops teaching how to use it. ● Leverage the models and frameworks developed over the last 10 years or so by the GovCMS initiative https://www.govcms.gov.au/ to propagate a interoperable CMS framework across the federal public sector. ● HMukurtu is content management software designed especially to empower indigenous communities “to manage, share, narrate, and exchange their digital heritage in culturally relevant and ethically-minded ways.” It works on the principle that “there is rarely just one story, one set of information, or one way of knowing cultural heritage materials.” ● "HMukurtu is content management software designed especially to empower indigenous communities ..." - These are important considerations, but Mukurtu is not an ideal technical solution for the problems (data lockin). ● "HMukurtu is content management software designed especially to empower indigenous communities ..." - Add as it is a CMS rather than a repository it may not make a good end-point for linking things (and yes the lock-in risk is very high particularly if it is used to encode

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>cultural access protocols -- these cannot be exported as standards as they cannot (and probably should not) be codified</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● a lot of organisations have their own work documented/archived (e.g. Elizabethan Theatre Trust, Back To Back Theatre), and a lot of artists do their own activities researching back (e.g. I just saw one looking at Deaf actors on Australian TV), and there are funding initiatives supporting more archival work (e.g. I just saw Churchill funded Lena Nalhous to do archive cultural diverse artwork), not in interoperable format (we've links with AusStage so we've perhaps more understanding of this), but it'd be good to be able to look to how there could be 'front door' to that, if interoperability not possible ● Open culture movement and the push for an Open Culture statement from UNESCO ● https://poetryarchive.org/ ● The above link (Poetry Archive UK) is a collection of sound recordings of poets reading their works (some of them Australian). There are also other archives like this, e.g. PennSound.

Activity 3: Roles and partners

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What other kinds of partners need to be involved?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● People who may not have the resources for archival networks - regional, community artists, those working outside the mainstream like small/medium arts orgs.. ● Regional and remote stakeholders (+2) ● Roles/Partners: Is there an Advisory/Stakeholder committee? AusStage has had this. It is not clear atm how there is representation of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Perspectives in terms of the data sovereignty, as well as other stakeholder perspectives, in terms of the 'nothing about us without us' and 'privacy' etc. aspects of the data in some of the A&Q. Then, given number of organisations/sectors, peak agencies in theatre and performance,

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>GLAM, etc. who can be interlink to industries, as well as archives (Film Sound Archive, etc.), etc., we link with in our data collection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Triangulation is needed here: facilitating the bringing together of research, data, communities. While it's principally a research/data infrastructure there are a range of user groups and communities and beneficiaries. It should learn from Indigenous Data program. ● indigenous First Nations traditional custodians, researchers and peak bodies ● "indigenous First Nations traditional custodians, researchers and peak bodies" - unis, galleries, venues (esp. theatre), companies (dance theatre etc), also production companies (Performing Lines, etc) ● Cultural institutions and Indigenous communities ● Peak First Nations creative and cultural orgs (+3) ● AIATSIS (+1) ● CMS Integration partners ● ASAL ● Creative Australia ● ADB for database design and management (and cross-pollination with AustLit/AusStage etc) but also their ongoing work in updating and reframing who is covered and how ● Heavy or regular users of AustLit/AusStage ● International Federation of Arts Councils and Cultural Agencies ● informed researchers in archive studies, 'decolonial' studies, and research data commons from outside Australia, in the Global South and East ● Any organisation that has developed expertise/experience in data management and sharing. Such as the ADB! ● GovCMS ● Small to medium orgs as well as large organisations ● general public: citizen science ● "general public: citizen science" - audiences? ● Public broadcasters (ABC and SBS) who may hold research-related materials

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who you talk to depends on how you define cultural heritage - if you're limiting to the artforms/creative practices in your definition vs. whether you're willing to broaden it to include screen, audio, digital media ● Association for the study of Australian Literature (+1) ● Australian Poetry Library at USyd: https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20190305152033/https://www.poetrylibrary.edu.au/ ● Given the feds fund national institutions on an ongoing basis, it would seem that this project of data commons needs to get on that government agenda. Beyond the initial grant, large though that is. (+1) ● Diversity Arts Australia ● Existing partners (like IbsenStage, Theatre Aotearoa) ● New Writers Australia entity that is emerging out of Creative Australia essential to engage with once that's announced later this year? (+1) ● Lit journals/mags and other literary archives ● Lit mags and journals eg Westerly Magazine (+1) ● Peak bodies for creative practitioners - on the 'lit' side, e.g. APA, ASA, SPN, ABA etc ● Australian Society of Authors/Australian Writers Guild and other professional bodies ● Media Arts Entertainment Alliance, Live Performance Australia and Australian Writers's Guild in terms of theatre and performance industry associations ● Informit, Trove, NLA, etc (Australian Dancing is now lost in the NLA website slightly which is a shame, but them too) ● archivists, state libraries, galleries, arts organisations (+1) ● GLAM sector - anyone who holds material records (+2) ● Writers Festivals and Writers Centres in each state and territory; ditto arts festivals, esp in the regions ● Festivals association (+1) ● "Writers Festivals and Writers Centres in each state and territory; ditto arts festivals, esp in the regions" - film festivals as well (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Writers Festivals and Writers Centres in each state and territory; ditto arts festivals, esp in the regions" - gaming repositories and collections (+1) ● artists and arts organisations ● Small to medium arts organisations (eg literary magazines like Australian Book Review, art galleries, theatre companies etc). (+1) ● Creative practitioners (+1) ● practitioners and artists ● Reinforce point made by others, creative artists and various other practitioners in the creative and cultural sectors. ● Industry bodies such as the ASA (+2) ● Great point about festivals, they are such a huge feature of our creative and cultural landscapes! ● Peak organisations such as the AAWP (Australasian Assoc. of Writing Programs) (+1) ● government like Creative Australia (+1) ● arts peak bodies across artforms and communities ● Creative Australia / state and territory arts departments ● Arts organisations with their own archives that could be better integrated into records/databases
<p>What other expertise/resources would benefit the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● People who can speak meaningfully to accessibility needs e.g. organisations like Vision Australia ● artists and practitioners from under-represented groups, particularly disability and cultural diversity ● Other organisations that have already established frameworks where identifiers and linked data are embedded ● archivists, those with formal training in cataloguing, databases, etc, formal museologists... as well as scholars, artists, laypeople, etc ● Staff to ensure data integrity ● The best website designers possible? ● Responding to AI suggestions - this is another place where universities can contribute in partnerships potentially (see for example

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>https://www.rmit.edu.au/research/centres-collaborations/centre-for-industrial-ai-research-and-innovation)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organisations which are really good at this kind of thing i.e. demography departments, ABS, and so on. ● Research vocabularies Australia ● Those leading operationalisation of Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Indigenous Data Governance. (+3) ● What is our First Nations involvement? I didn't recognise many First Nations scholars, artists or stakeholders in our current list. If that is true (?) that is a problem. Should we build a shortlist to contact? ● funding for hosting websites ● Who you talk to depends on how you define cultural heritage - if you're limiting to the artforms/creative practices in your definition vs. whether you're willing to broaden it to include screen, audio, digital media ● Raising awareness and gaining new users for the research infrastructure through communication and outreach ● Web developers at IbsenStage who have created other functions that Ausstage could potentially benefit from.
<p>Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Groups like Vision Australia and the Deafness Forum for access etc (+3) ● artists with disabilities, allies (+1) ● University management agreeing to investment. ● university libraries having direct links for research ● The largest data entry contributors and those who crunch the data to create reports and research outcomes ● The best website designers possible? (+1) ● Researchers who have already completed projects that have cross-walked this kind of data using bespoke/experimental methods (+1) ● Regional and remote stakeholders (+2) ● Public libraries and their peak bodies (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Past and existing projects that have already attempted similar work (e.g. ACDE & HuNI) ● Open access is really important! ● Non-binary taskforce to consult on projects related to gender (+3) ● National specialist networks such as the ADB State-based and interest-based working parties. ● Migrants ● Input from international end-users ● historians ● First Nations (+2) ● Copyright and intellectual property holders ● content management system specialists ● Co-design with community who created, own, or have stakes in the data/data sovereignty/etc., ● capacity for engagement and impact statements/indicators/measures ● Broad sector perspectives, inc commercial (booksellers, production companies) as well as service (writers orgs, editors, publishers) and artists. ● Avoiding silos. E.g. recordings of Indigenous song are important to musicologists, performance studies, Indigenous studies, but also linguists. Interoperability at the level of the HASS&I RDC should be a goal. (+1) ● arts journalists/critics/commentators (+1) ● Anticipated end-users such as Creative Australia (+1) ● "Non-binary taskforce to consult on projects related to gender" - 100% agree with this: community consultation is vital in this area. ● Those already running larger/rich archives and databases as well as those who use them regularly ● the input of archive scholars could be really productive - that field is currently having a 'moment' and there may be creative approaches to the pragmatic concerns (see, for example, https://www.qmu.ac.uk/news-and-events/events-listing/shaking-the-archive/ (+1)) ● Small to medium arts orgs and other arts organisations with their own archives/databases

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Schools students, undergraduates (+1) ● Really important to have HDR students and ECRs engaging in the creative arts research infrastructure. (+3) ● People working outside traditional publishing networks (i.e., self publishing authors). ● HDR and ECRs ● Creative artists (+1) ● archivists ● Any people or organisations who create or contribute to culture and cultural history ● Teachers/educators from the primary through secondary into tertiary space

APPENDIX 2: WORKSHOP 2 RESPONSES

Outcome 1: Provide connected and coherent interfaces to data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Harmonise data models and schemas</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AusStage has distinct tables as an events database, including most recently a financial table designed to aggregate data and therefore has the potential to offer a national overview of funding. I imagine we need to carefully consider the aim and capabilities of the database in order to maximise the schemas as part of harmonising this infrastructure. ● Clear and engaging pathways / curatorial to support data navigation and use ● Are there any International Standards Organisation (ISO) standards that apply to data harmonisation? (+4) ● What does database mean here? Structured data or data stored with a DBMS? ● Need expert stakeholders input to develop a sustainable model (+1) ● I'm not sure which 'data models' you're talking about harmonising here: is it all artforms and which data models and schemas? I'm not across a kind of map (given my knowledge is artform specific) and so it's hard to know whether this proposed ambition is feasible, or properly representative. ● Making the methodologies and processes of the existing data infrastructures visible, so that other smaller, nascent and new data sources can use, connect in and be built in relation to them ● Harmonising assumes that the standard to be harmonised to has been established. Will community consultation include vocab and metadata consultation? (+2) ● Capability and accessible information to support users to understand how the data functions and how to interact with it ● "Capability and accessible information to support users to understand how the data functions and how to interact with it " - I agree. Raising awareness in order to build capability is very important.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How to capture and represent under-served and under-represented activities? Existing datasets tend to have particular established relationships and infrastructures (+1) ● Finding ways to remove the paywall, ensuring federal government funding, would be essential. The people benefit in tangible and intangible ways from all this work. This should therefore be supported by the people. It's part of our cultural memory which informs the present and the future. ● Unlikely that data models and schema can be harmonised effectively across heterogeneous technology stacks. Consider instead propagating a consistent CMS framework and migrating existing assets to it. ● "Unlikely that data models and schema can be harmonised effectively..." - not 100% sure what a CMS is but sounds promising ● Harmonisation' will require shared understanding / agreement between different users about purpose ● Data models should 'play well' with data viz tools (+3) ● Geo-location can be difficult for digital work. ● Creative arts data is messy. Resist the urge to harmonise everything. You'll lose nuance. ● Harmonising is great, but also respecting difference to not shoehorn data into a shared model (+1) ● harmonising data requires harmonising metadata, and metadata standards ● Existing visual art databases: galleries that collect art (300+ across Australia), Victorian Collections, WA Collections. (+1) ● I heard "the data" and "the databases" as though there were only two databases that you're considering.. Sooo, uh - there's more between heaven and earth Horatio. ● "I heard "the data" and "the databases" as though there were only two databases that you're considering.. " - I think this is useful to bear in mind for future planning - if/when the scope of this expands beyond AustLit and AusStage, what are the other data models that might need to link? Are there choices that you can make now that will help streamline that process down the track?

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There will likely be people, projects and organisations repeated across databases, potentially with different names or spellings ● Look at the experience of GovCMS in propagating a consistent framework that can be themed for different implementations ● Peak body benchmarking data - Public galleries Association of Victoria, National Public Galleries Alliance. ● ACDE_A (information architecture) provided a model for cultural data integration that retained the unique properties of existing databases ● Government arts agencies - arts organisations reporting data. ● lol. Existing databases Ausstage and AusLit. From page to stage. ● Exploring ethical use of AI? (+1) ● I heard 'the data ● Identifiers for people and content and organisations will be essential (+1) ● Will establishing any kinds of multilingual and multicultural metadata be part of this phase? (i.e. all knowledge categories should not be Western culture /English-language-based) (+2) ● wOULD running the platform similar to a library database be one way of capturing all the moving parts? Have training sites as well as data bases. (+1) ● We build harmony between metadata so that the connections and relations between the data assets can be reinforced, expanded and contested by researchers, and research-informed publics ● Perhaps the notion of harmonising data schemas is unrealistic. A more productive approach might be to provide a common framework to support consolidation and contestation. ● Design a standard distribution of a mainstream open source CMS as a target framework
Pilot an API(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I don't know what this means in practice, but it sounds problematic to me. I think the IP issues this raises are enormous and were I an artist, esp. with suspicions around AI right now, Im not sure we'd get agreement to this ● "I don't know what this means in practice, but it sounds problematic to me. I think the IP issues this raises are enormous ..." Different

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>concerns apply to archiving works themselves vs. the metadata/bibliographic info about them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preferably no authentication required (for reading data), or at least limited authentication-free access to encourage experimentation & aid training ● Tools or examples to help researchers assemble/analyse/share datasets from the API ● Support/document API with live runnable examples, such as in Jupyter notebooks (eg ARDC Community Data Lab, GLAM Workbench) ● Restructuring the team and processes, as Caroline noted, so it is led by First Nations intellectuals and experts. ● Invest in good API documentation (not just another Swagger interface) that includes useful examples ● Provide (authenticated) write as well as read access via API to allow things like annotations and links to be created. ● API is a new term to me. I am sceptical of data harvesting as it seems to reinstate all the same old hierarchies. And again: which databases are you referring to and who or what is missing from those? I feel like this whole consultation is a bit of a stab in the dark because i'm not a data expert - I'm a creative arts practitioner/scholar - and you're asking me to comment on things that are beyond my expertise without taking the time to educate me properly about the field/terminology/opportunities. Can you excite me about the possibilities with an example from overseas perhaps and then ask me whether I think that would work for my artform?. ● Ethical frameworks in place to ensure data security. ● Clear licensing of metadata to facilitate API use ● Raising awareness among underrepresented minority communities about all this data and what can be done with it, its potential, would be important. ● people with skills in technical aspects as well as humanities research ethics ● be careful thinking that an API is an app. technical access is not a user experience. (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Share identifiers/paths between web interface and API, so that moving between representations is straightforward (content negotiation?) ● Will this require identification of how fields relate to each other across databases? Ie a first stage in harmonisation ● Is it more of a 'data warehouse' than an API? (+1) ● Share API design docs to gather feedback at an early stage ● Both databases do very different things in the sense that AusStage has digitally recreated theatre spaces that no longer exist so there's a lot to consider in terms of a pilot ● How will you define the kinds of interrogations (and even, the framing of queries and keywords) that will be relevant to different end-users and keep the possibilities for querying dynamically updated as end-user needs and generations evolve? Especially as AI technologies evolve, user expectations will increase in relation to the functionality of interfaces to data ● An ethical consideration around interrogation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What constraints might there be on making and sharing inferences from data, e.g. using NLP, that might surface sensitive information, e.g. identity-related features that the author or artist might not have publicly shared but that could be inferred from features of their language and/or their connections and interests? (+1) ● "An ethical consideration around interrogation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What constraints might there be on making and sharing inferences from data..." - good point: though isn't that more an application issue? ● Original permissions to collect/use data did not envisage this. Is exposure via API in keeping with permissions already granted? ● all databases have an API but not all of them are open - AustLit is the exception in the field, so it will be essential that it becomes open for the project to work.
Align features across databases to give a more consistent user experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What about film and tv etc which relate to both books and plays - ACMI would be great to involve ● things shouldn't be wildly different; the main thing is access methods to be fairly transparent and easy; but Im not 100% sure this is necessary. I'll leave to others

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● certain search functionalities may be standardised but diversity and innovation would be comprised if there was a mandated requirement ● Design features to support consistent navigation experiences - while also ensuring accessibility ● What is the social interface you will design? ● One challenge is that things like genre can use art-form specific language (+1) ● "One challenge is that things like genre can use art-form specific language" - true, but that's often good. As a single eg the ridiculous use of "to curate" outside of art galleries is ridiculous (curatorial is not simply to edit or select). So actually keeping those terms while data is otherwise but together would help nuance in a helpful way, I hope ● "One challenge is that things like genre can use art-form specific language" - This can be a big issue when moving between arts based databases as 'art terms' are often not universally applied. For example, Works on Paper may not be registered in that way at another gallery, they may be divided by media instead (etching, drawing etc) ● This seems to be a limited approach only taking into account 2 databases. What about other data sources? How will these be built in over time? ● Depends a lot on harmonising data models and schemas. (LH column) ● being able to search by various types of marker may improve issues around the use of varied terms as used by each organisation ● Consistency of experience/access is more important than consistency of language etc, just noting that many different artforms will ideally feed into the database ● If authentication is required, provide a shared service across platforms ● Embed structured data in web records (eg JSONLD, meta tags) to support use of tools like Zotero

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UQ library has a great project with Indigenous meta data at the moment. This should become standard practice for all meta data now ● Unlikely this can be done across heterogenous technology stacks ● Music databases might benefit from signposting text/author contributors to music more as these often intersect with austlit/ausstage contributors (+1) ● Obviously would love to see this but how is it possible given repositories are housed by different institutions and they don't often cooperate? ● "Obviously would love to see this but how is it possible given repositories are housed by different institutions and they don't often cooperate?" - Hence need something like ARDC to drive cooperation ● Quality metadata is crucial. There are some excellent and evolving standards that new infrastructure can tap into, adopt, learn from. (+2) ● Tertiary institutional repositories are good places to start for examples of metadata alignment with government reporting - just to see what might be learned, not necessarily copied ● Identification of useful features and mapping will be really important ● Allow downloads of search results in machine-readable form (eg JSON, CSV) -- as an interface component as well as API ● Consistent user experiences across databases are not top of my list - researchers are skilled enough at navigating each. And key special features tailored to the aims of each matter. (+1) ● Also, access at different points might be affected by external events, for eg death of artist ... and restrictions about use of their names and or materials. ● user training developed with evaluation and efficacy in mind. ● Share annotations across platforms, eg so that tags comments on a work in Trove could show up in interface ● harmony in metadata for data harvests is important to build relations between data assets held in different collections and archives. Building relations is core humanities research.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● •Aligning features suggests that users are themselves aligned, but different users will certainly have different needs in terms of the sophistication of access functions and responses from the database. Are there user groupings proposed in existing standards that could be applied and could be the foundation for different design features for users with varying levels of language, as well as other kinds of accessibility feature? (+1) ● ONE thing I'm noticing here is the absence of any interaction design and games people. If they were here, we might have a more nuanced understanding of what a user experience might be? (+1) ● Again, I think the existing features first need to be interrogated for bias, inclusivity, and diverse end-user appropriateness before alignment is undertaken ● See HuNI as a public open access networked interface
<p>Investigate sustainability of the databases and asymmetry of access</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Just to reiterate this is the big issue; no solutions, sorry, except commitments from host institutions (+1) ● Open access is the ideal, and would see much greater use of the data internationally too. More acknowledgment of the costs of long term maintenance in research funding is one area for improvement. (+1) ● Sustainability can only come by building upon existing library information systems that are curated and managed by experts in this field of information systems; bespoke databases need ways therefore to be added and expand the communities of use. ● "Sustainability can only come by building upon existing library information systems that are curated and managed by experts in this field of information systems..." - this used to be the case with Theatre Aotearoa but it proved problematic as entries were not always well vetted, etc, and needed a fair bit of editing later. It is hard to insist on high level training if they are volunteers ● Open access has to be the way forward (+1) ● Sustainability in terms of funding and hosting - and understanding the capacity required to create and maintain a national database – are crucial issues that have to be addressed beyond funding and political cycles. Is there a commitment to this work as ongoing infrastructure? (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One thing that could be interesting to explore is how the database could ultimately encourage/facilitate collaborations, as well as capturing information about earlier collaborations –that would depend partly on access across all kinds of art forms ● I've seen other databases (I can't remember which one sorry! It as mentioned at a recent conference) draw on volunteers to assist with database entry. It would require strong community engagement, but is one option (obvs in an ideal world everyone is paid for their labour though!) ● An OA model would be required as a long-term aspiration (+1) ● How do you make sure that the decisions you make now are going to stay correct/be able to be stood by in the future? What kind of infrastructure do we want people to inherit in 5, 10, 20 years time? What kind of infrastructure will enable other databases/art forms to be integrated in the future? ● Advocacy for institutional/university recognition that such data infrastructure is essential to core business of teaching and learning and higher degree by research, research, and public engagement. (+2) ● Yes, that sounds nice, but to go back to points I made at the last session, who is the 'user' here and why are they prioritised so consistently over the rights holders/artists? Creative arts is not free. It's not produced without resources.If you turned this on its head it might say: Give artists a consistent experience in monitoring and giving permissions as well as receiving appropriate compensation for how their 'data' is accessed/used. (+1) ● "Yes, that sounds nice, but to go back to points I made at the last session, who is the 'user' here and why are they prioritised so consistently over the rights holders/artists?" - nice point. maybe that's more projects to be run once parts or much of the database has been trialled, and then use this to value add ● Sustainability isn't "anyone can create an account and edit the database. You actually have to fund community engagement if you want to sustain the community. I've seen this fail before with the DAAO.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lock-in with database models/systems may impact sustainability. ● Contrary to many here, I have concerns about it being open access, particularly when it comes to Indigenous Data Sovereignty ● Access for arts organisations needs to be free. I can see different access based on annual turnover and or stakeholder group (arts org, government, university etc). (+2) ● Targeted interventions & strategies to address specific needs and asymmetries (+1) ● There is asymmetry of access as an equity issue but also asymmetry of access by design so that for example Indigenous knowledge holders could have access to some data but others not empowered to have access can access only versions of the data that iare publicly available. ● Asymmetry of access comes from (lack of) awareness of what data(bases) exist and how they can be useful for individuals and groups as well as design features. How will awareness and practical user skills be cultivated, e.g. among secondary students including in regional and remote Australia? (+1) ● Movements in OA, especially publicly funded research outputs, may be useful here ● Lack of access to digitised materials is also an access issue - click through links to online material is what students want. ● Data integrity is key to the question of sustainability, as Maggie Nolan pointed out and this is central to end-users well beyond research. I think it's important to look at how Australian developments are positioned internationally because this opens up broader opportunities for funding through collaboration. (+2) ● Setting up so it's harder to be dismantled or abandoned due to a funding or policy decision ● "Setting up so it's harder to be dismantled or abandoned due to a funding or policy decision" - can have reverse issue to; old URLs hidden in servers and impossible to delete

Outcome 2: Identify and fill gaps in the data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Implement Indigenous Data Sovereignty and governance strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standalone ICIP legislation coming in. Patricia Adje is leading this (+1) ● AustLit already has BlackWords that has been overseen by First Nations researchers and indexers. Talk to those people. They have done excellent work in that space. (+1) ● Use existing work already being done in the sector (+1) ● This will also need to consider Indigenous Cultural & Intellectual Property (ICIP) (+2) ● what is data sovereignty, actually? That's a complex thing. Yes, great to have a pilot to investigate it and to prioritise First Nations... but this looks harder than it sounds. I worry about this. (+1) ● "what is data sovereignty, actually? That's a complex thing." - See: https://www.maiamnayriwingara.org/mnw-principles ● "what is data sovereignty, actually? That's a complex thing." - " See: https://www.maiamnayriwingara.org/mnw-principles" Thanks Kit. This looks wonderful and it would have been nice to have some more time to hear about this rather than assuming knowledge today. The idea that 'indigenous communities retain the right to decide which sets of data require active governance and maintain the right to not participate in data processes inconsistent with the principles asserted in the Communique' could be usefully applied as a model for how all rights holders in the arts are consulted about what happens to the creative work (or commercially confidential info about it) that is termed 'data' and digitised by others. ● Recognising colonial load when connecting to existing First Nations-led entities and projects, and practitioners - there needs to be consideration of resourcing stakeholders to engage and provide guidance. (+1) ● Ensure the navigation and pathways into the data (and its visible infrastructure) are co-designed, navigable and culturally relevant ● some of the challenges we are currently facing in arts archives at our institution is the ability to connect individuals with data about them/their families due to practical issues, such as tech literacy and also geographical placement.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tapping into practitioner-led conversations (noting that people need to be resourced to connect and provide guidance) ● International users also matter in considering changes to ontologies - keeping them in the loop can be difficult ● relationship between contestation and crowdsourcing (of relations actual data assets needs to be investigated. So too the roles of libraries and museums etc as "participatory" knowledge organisations that engage in addressing alternative facts, histories, etc ● What can you learn from ATSIDA about data rematrication? ● https://www.atsida.edu.au/ ● could be a good thing to be aware of ● Indigenous led design applying principles of Indigenous Data Sovereignty in other sectors such as health research ● Plain english, culturally relevant language and accessible guidance and navigation pathways ● Don't use discipline-specific jargon; plain English; make navigation and user pathways accessible ● Open access and direct harnessing of connections and relations, both agreement and contestation, between data assets is needed ● This is not a "gap" in the data, it's a higher-level design/governance issue - in many ways I think the individual steps you've identified here aren't really about gaps in the data but more about decisions and experimentation that should come before and inform the steps identified in the previous breakout re: data harmonisation ● I think ways of working and interacting are really important to reflect on collectively before embarking on co-design and making business around Indigenous data (+1) ● Think small scale and practical while keeping an eye on the big picture ● We've (ALIA) found a huge appetite for change in this area - harnessing this appetite has been a task, corralling efforts as well as raising the bar in general about awareness and respect. ● I'm working on a project where aside from needing the right cultural connections, to do FULLY I would probably need to trek out many

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>many miles to a regional community. At least for the project I'm working on, this isn't a possibility. Data sovereignty involves finding the sovereigns so as to speak, and that's hard and contested... but do-able (+!)</p>
<p>Consult with researchers, peak bodies, and communities to develop human-rights based approach to new ontologies and vocabularies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Equal representation - ensure all artform peaks are represented - and both state and national bodies." - This is essential. I understand the logic to trial with two big players, but if all the art forms aren't represented it risks needing to redo the work all over again ● "Equal representation - ensure all artform peaks are represented - and both state and national bodies." - "This is essential. I understand the logic to trial with two big players, but if all the art forms aren't represented it risks needing to redo the work all over again" - Agree. Could it be a selected mix of small and large organisations to trial and mix of forms? (+1) ● simply put, making this real rather than rhetorical, esp. with peak bodies, is the challenge; I guess this can only be achieved by quite active pressure to ensure ideals are put into practice (+1) ● Establish an ethnic and gender diversity taskforce. (+3) ● Peak / industry bodies can provide datasets they contribute to, or know of, to ensure gaps are addressed. ● "Right to data held about them" - in the arts sector we need this extended to be aggregate data about the sector. ● consulting with peak bodies is admirable but you're biasing the dominant cultural art forms through this strategy. (+1) ● "consulting with peak bodies is admirable but you're biasing the dominant cultural art forms through this strategy." - there is part of this where the very idea of a big data approach is to some degree arguably in tension with the very concept of dispersed, localised, community held (in place) sovereignty ● The idea of authorship and the way 'works' are approached in the future will need to expand to incorporate more layers of community collaboration, endorsement and representation for diverse communities and their contributions to be acknowledged ● Vocabularies change over time, would need to be able to revisit/refresh this when necessary (+4)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Think about how to consult at scale across the sector. Not sure we're getting coverage across the institutional outfits ● Build on existing ontologies ● AustLit has a Writing Disability in Australia dataset, led by Jess White at UniSA. She is leading another ARC-funded project partnering with AustLit again. So, there is work happening in this space. ● would be worthwhile connecting to community groups especially where a sense of recording unofficial archives can enrich 'the data' For example Australian Queer Archives ● whose rights? ● There are many gaps in historical data ● yes please. Sounds good. ● Data sovereignty protections should be extended to all people. There are many people in our communities who are vulnerable and whom unprincipled data-sharing could expose to risk. In this respect, the human-rights based approach is exceptionally important, but it needs to not make assumptions about those who are vulnerable to harm. For example, anyone from any group might have mental health issues that make them vulnerable to data-related harms, and this includes creative practitioners from across all communities. (+3) ● How will sociocultural and sociopolitical considerations be taken into account? E.g. from a linguistic perspective, the language known as "Persian" is also called "Farsi". The latter is a colonial name for the former. How will you be able to identify issues such as this in terms of the historical origin of names and present-day sociopolitical resonances they might have? (+1) ● "How will sociocultural and sociopolitical considerations be taken into account?..." -Gender identity also falls into this category, and thinking about gender transition and affirmation in a database context is vital.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Pilot these ontologies via community co-design and targeted data entry efforts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● on the previous board there was a suggestion to run various versions of these as stand alone projects. This seems wise to me (and could get funding for each one). It would however mean doing this is "bits"... but that seems inevitable (+1) ● The term 'co-design' rings alarm bells for me. It is rarely if ever that. I'm sorry to be sceptical but their are some buzz words that instil a great lack of confidence in so-called 'consultation' teams and this is one of them. Are we working in the design discipline here? So let's just talk about consultation and collaboration instead. (+1) ● you'll need to fund his. All the discussion and co-reporting from the column to the right will mean diddly squat if you end up producing a bund of stand alone resources that people are meant to 'copy' in order to undertake the effort. ● Gallery databases are a useful guide for visual arts data ontology. Copyright for visual arts a major issue re digitisation and public access. ● will there be scope for smaller scale projects to be beneficiaries if they are evolving community co-design of data entry with indigenous artists? (+1) ● Targeted data entry can work well in delimited projects with fundable outcomes (+1) ● Targeted data entry efforts can be very effective - the National Dictionary of Biography has done this very well. (+1) ● Maybe work with the Indigenous Voice infrastructure to develop pilot projects ● "Maybe work with the Indigenous Voice infrastructure to develop pilot projects" - interesting. Maybe ask Marilyn if she (and/or others) agree ● This is a terrific idea for discovering new concepts and connections for inclusion in ontologies (+1) ● working with organisations and communities that have culturally safe protocols in place for restricted access of data (stories, images, performance etc) (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I wonder if everyone here is comfortable in their understanding of what ontologies are and how they work? For end-user consultations, this will need to be made very clear. (+2) ● In addition to identifying and filling gaps, the integrity of existing data needs to be ensured. AusStage has a specific approach to data entry (+1) ● "In addition to identifying and filling gaps, the integrity of existing data needs to be ensured. AusStage has a specific approach to data entry" - And it is one that makes tracking digital work and reception difficult. ● Pilot approach can tackle issues related to coherence of data models, too: audiobooks are an example of a cultural form that is both book and performed work and working out how to index them in/across AustLit and AusStage would highlight issues and also the need for multi-disciplinary data (+2) ● Could this involve AIATSIIS? ● First Nations First consultations are currently underway to inform establishment of a self-determined entity within Creative Australia ● Include specific and explicit goals and standards that you want to achieve. Often goals around data sovereignty and access are so broad that they're practically meaningless ● Experimentation and piloting small pieces of work will enable the iterative development of solutions to the first set of issues re: data harmonisation - this can inform the bigger decisions rather than those being made first ● Please be sure to include secondary students in this community co-design effort. They are the data users and producers of the future. ● "Please be sure to include secondary students in this community co-design effort. They are the data users and producers of the future." - Especially Indigenous HEd Students. ● Include a function within the database to flag incorrect or incomplete data so that users who identify gaps have an easy and quick means of notifying.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Longer term: collect born-digital data by developing automated data ingestion/spidering options to gather data, de-duplicate it, and synthesise new records</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will creative practitioners be able to resist data ingestion about them if they chose to do so? (+1) ● See HuNI as a public open access networked interface ● Data integrity is key to this entire project ● How will copyright be managed if data is spidered from sources that may be under copyright protection? ● tools to develop automated ingestion would be great, but a lot of cultural data remains proprietary; how would this be navigated? (+1) ● "tools to develop automated ingestion would be great, but a lot of cultural data remains proprietary; how would this be navigated?" - Good question and one that needs to be resolved. ● I would oppose this being done in an automated fashion. Much better if automation identifies paired entries to look at... but dont trust algorithmic processes alone; they are inherently problematic still (and rather counter to what is proposed here) (+4) ● Ingest data about recently published works from the National EDeposit Scheme via the Trove API ● I don't know what you're talking about. Who is ingesting spiders? How do you expect us to give sophisticated feedback if you haven't educated us about your discipline specific terminology? Honestly, it's infuriating and feels like you're wasting an opportunity as well as our time. You've clearly already made up your mind about what you intend to do and don't want to hear our opinions because you're obfuscating, in addition to not letting us have a proper conversation and insisting we speak to you through these dumb stickers. ● There may be AI tools that can help with data matching and de-duping ● Need to engage with work being done in digital preservation ● Need to accommodate a range of access conditions and privacy issues ● born digital sounds like a shortcut for essentially event hosting metadata. Consider fragility of born digital artwork outside the collections of austage and astlii. ● How will this sit alongside Indigenous Data Sovereignty principles?

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Would love to see GLAM sector data synthesised into a national collection
(other responses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I can't speak to Indigenous data sovereignty and governance except insofar as it comes up in my own work with communities identify intersectionality as First Nations and POC, CALD, LGBTIQA+, and d/Deaf, disabled, and neurodiverse. The practical considerations are the 'nothing about us without us,' the accessibility, the multiple and conflicting access requirements, the diverse views within a diverse community in which there are underrepresented groups within the underrepresented groups. ● The automated/spidering is an issue, there are misreadings, errors, etc. that require a critical interrelationships with the data, in particular a lot of 'about us without us' data, or 'absences' that aren't real absences, that is a long story of what is silenced when, where, how, and why for different groups within the groups. The practical solution is still the research/technical people who identify in dialogue with community who identify in the steering committee, to look at the sharp edge of how to engage with a lot of the technological options that are being proposed, relative to their cultural and social implications for historically marginalised and intersectionality historically marginalised group that I do archival research with. ● I note we have not been talking about money. A lot of DPOs, including Indigenous-led DPOs do not have a lot, do not like to have expertise drawn on for free all the time, but, concurrently, report to use that they do not like the constant requests for data/expertise 'for a woolies voucher' etc. So that's a practical consideration about ways of relating to research/technical community in terms of engagement that has in the past been sub optimal (and may still be in some Uni/Big 4 consult contexts today)

Outcome 3: Increasing coherence and collaboration across groups and disciplines working with mediated data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Design and deliver a series of workshops and resources for researchers as well as for artists, authors and citizen scientists</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● pay people as consultants if you value their contribution. (+1) ● When doing 'engagement' make sure there are clear benefits and pathways for participants - and always share back outcomes - some groups get regularly 'consulted' and left out of the outcomes (+2) ● "When doing 'engagement' make sure there are clear benefits and pathways for participants - and always share back outcomes - some groups get regularly 'consulted' and left out of the outcomes" - Agree, consider the benefit you can provide to any groups consulted, not just the benefit gained ● Yes, please. But please don't leave this to the end - it would be good for this to happen early and in time to feedback into the design of the whole project. (+1) ● One dataset that already exists in terms of documenting practice is the set of creative practice based PhD theses produced by graduate researchers in our universities. ● It will need to be made clear that this is not som sort of Wikipedia. A free for all. ● A free workshop is not an engagement strategy (+1) ● I'm keen to see even broader profile boosting for these databases, increasing awareness in media organisations, government and the broader education system (+3) ● Make sure any 'opportunities' that draw on creative practice recognise and remunerate practitioner contributions (+2) ● Make sure to target these workshops to people in regional areas. Reaching out to local libraries/councils is one way to get the word out about opportunities like this. (+2) ● Provide formal training and recognition when 'building capability' - connect to other pathways ● Looking at the comments here I don't think there's clarity on whether these workshops/resources relate to inputting data or using data ● "Looking at the comments here I don't think there's clarity on whether these workshops/resources relate to inputting data or using data" - Maybe these workshops should target both (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Workshops at researcher conferences are important even if engagement can seem low - it's important that new generations of scholars are kept in the loop ● managing copyright when digitising visual art ● "managing copyright when digitising visual art" - And digital performance ● This needs to be done in a discipline specific way - linking to communities ● Draw on the skills of libraries in delivering public-facing education programs (+1) ● deliver workshops at at ResBaz, make the most of inter and transdisciplinary spaces ● Long Term development of a self-help knowledge base ● Focus on two cohorts -- PhDs and ECRs in first instance. ● Community roundtables are a very effective public engagement mechanism that may work particularly well in regional and remote areas ● Data entry protocols will be important. Also ensuring those doing the data entry understand how it will be used - otherwise they can unknowingly miss or misinterpret fields ● Have a rollout of training courses for all collection houses, arts orgs, arts hub etc for take up. ● Not all solutions are software. You need staff to help navigate. (+1) ● identifying impact from data ● Who is the community? Need language, aspiration and vision around who is in frame. Principally researchers (as first order NCRIS), but this has the potential to bring in a much broader range of participants -- including 'industry' broadly defined. Workshops could themselves be co-designed with community stakeholders involved in planning. ● Staff can also help with the facilitation of research skills for all interested and ongoing available upskilling ● Workshops/resources for integration into undergraduate curricula could be interesting ● Perhaps include educators, e.g. school teachers and principals, here as well, as a key interface to some user groups? (+2)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Perhaps include educators, e.g. school teachers and principals, here as well, as a key interface to some user groups?" - Definitely! AustLit does outreach to schools, but something larger and more capacious would be very welcome ● Who does this well? Look outside the sector -- incl STEM [and what STEM could stand to gain from creative arts] (+2) ● Spend money on a targeted advertising campaign. Make it sexy, relatable and why it is important. ● sure. but what type? how? dunno. Ive been reading about de Quincey's Triple Alice of late. Is that a model worth considering? maybe not (+1) ● "sure. but what type? how? dunno. Ive been reading about de Quincey's Triple Alice of late. Is that a model worth considering? maybe not" - as a transdisciplinary collaborative social experiment, this is a useful model for future work. ● There are already loads of resources ● Collaborative workshops can be very successful, Also workshops associated with events which are not obviously core audience can be beneficial.
<p>Develop capacity to annotate records</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Connecting / partnering with capability building programs that resource and recognise participant contributions ● there are many successful annotation tools for images, for videos etc. available that could be better socialised (+1) ● This would be good but begs the question: who can annotate; how to stop misinformation or bad actors? ● Trove is the obvious model here and would have some great insights about volunteer inputs - less moderation needed than we'd think? (+1) ● Classically this is the province of content management systems (CMS) (+1) ● Annotation is only going to be feasible and ubiquitous on a consistent node graph ● Annotate but also link and cross-reference, e.g. in a knowledge graph (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who do you need buy-in from here. GLAM too? What's the process for consulting for win-win. (+1) ● Only plausible approach to ubiquitous annotation across implementations is a CMS consistent framework (+1) ● "Only plausible approach to ubiquitous annotation across implementations is a CMS consistent framework" - It's unclear to me (maybe I'm just being dense?) whether what we're discussing here is the parallel improvement of existing databases or the creation of a new one ● Careful consideration of gatekeeping to ensure sustainability ● This is a great idea. Agree there needs to be someone who's paid to check the entries and ensure they've been entered/formatted properly ● Be clear about the difference between A) annotating and correcting that modifies the material itself, which requires security and version control (like in Trove) and B) tools for 'stand-off' annotation which enable anyone to annotate anything without modifying it, but which requires robust granular addressing within text or media or DB record - eg: Here are my notes on this video where I've tagged every time the speaker mentions my topic of interest. ● AustLit has just set up a system for community data input (+1) ● Well, DAAO got rid of the large collection of annotations, and simultaneously opened it up again in the new database. This capacity while admirable isn't necessarily an automatic benefit. (+1) ● How do we bridge the gap between technical capability with data / systems, and subject and content expertise / lived experience? ● moderating is really important for data integrity - but allowing people to have control data about them is so important and a massive opportunity (+1) ● talk about building an army of record annotators or data entry people sounds aspirational and ethically dubious. It brings to mind the 'data awe' of 'data cleaning back in the early 2000s. ● annotation can add value within a community but would also need moderation over time, so an additional layer of human-centric activity

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Annotation is extremely important because we might need to flag specific contexts for data because data can be dynamic, eg, financial data (and comparing data across periods in this respect) ● Annotation would be very valuable as long as this operated as part of model that ensured checking the datta ● Ideally annotation tools using NLP, image recognition etc to support efficient data annotation and linkage would be ARDC-developed- and -owned and would not draw on cloud AI providers for reasons of data protection and long-term sustainability and control (+1) ● obviously, though I think this needs to be done by staff. O/s of that, having an option to request such changes is the way to go ● Vision of semantic annotation an semantic linking of annotations across implementations would require a consistent CMS framework. ● This has been done many times before ● ARDC have developed an image annotation workbench based on IIIF
<p>Longer term: curate opportunities for creative uses of creative data through artists-in-residence for both databases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://grattanstreetpress.com/books/small-data-is-beautiful/ ● "https://grattanstreetpress.com/books/small-data-is-beautiful/" - It sure is! But I think there's small data to be found in large data, as well. ● "https://grattanstreetpress.com/books/small-data-is-beautiful/" - "It sure is! But I think there's small data to be found in large data, as well." - indeed, creative potential in both directions ● there's plenty of models of material collections (libraries, museums, etc) productively using artists in residence, so look to those models; no reason these cant go online. Im a fan of the dance ones like the reworking of Hijikata's butoh-fu or the retagings / reconstructions of historic modernist ballets (Nijinsky, Nijinska, etc). Also of course fantastic First Nations work in museums (Yuki Kihara for eg, who does performative work) (+2) ● "there's plenty of models of material collections (libraries, museums, etc) productively using artists in residence, so look to those models..." - I'm keen on seeing really outlandishly data-driven approaches: how do you visualise data as an interactive sculpture? How do you turn bibliographical records about works set on the

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>Nullarbor into a soundscape? How can you plant and grow works about the Mallee?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● You should be able to start this sooner rather than later. There is already lots of data to explore. Get the data viz creatives in early ● "You should be able to start this sooner rather than later. There is already lots of data to explore. Get the data viz creatives in early" - Agree! This isn't something that has to wait for the longer term. It's a great idea to get started with now. ● Can build arts promotion and deeper understanding of the impact of creative arts in society via this program of opportunities ● and also making sure the gaps/less represented data also get expressed through these - real opportunities to hear less loud voices ● Could be various project-based residencies - curators, collaborations etc. ● What about 'researchers-in-residence'? I think it makes sense to provide explicit support to core user bases first (+5) ● I love the idea of writers-in-residence or other artists in residence to make new work by using the data creatively. This would also be good for raising the profile of the ARDC. (+1) ● Funding, funding, funding for this and all other aspects of this pillar/board (+1) ● May also encourage making creative arts activity and output more openly accessible over time ● and collaborations between data researchers and artists? (+2) ● Yes, please. I love this idea. (+2) ● Also student internships would be a great idea (+3) ● "Also student internships would be a great idea" - AustLit currently supports a wide range of student internships, and it is wonderful! Some of the more recent projects that students have worked on extensively include the Australian Writing and Rock Music project and the forthcoming preppers and AI projects. We also publish outcomes with student interns who have produced superlative work. (+1) ● This would help to show the potential, and to reinforce the importance of data integrity

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Including inter-arts residencies (so pairs of artists across two or more artforms) would be lovely here. (+3) ● "Including inter-arts residencies (so pairs of artists across two or more artforms) would be lovely here." - while this has merit, I'd actually say no. One already has a cross media thing here with data/archive going into art. To further complicate it with interarts would, to my mind, make it unnecessarily complex and less accessible. But maybe with the right people (esp. if they have worked together before) ● Creative use of creative data -- partnering with GLAM and other NCRIS could spark really interesting cross flows. ● Other parts of the HASS&I RDC have or will be building ML tools for text and images that could be used. And there are lots of open source tools ● Love this idea -b let's get good data to work with ● AustLit sort of does this with research projects that have active researcher engagement to develop specific outcomes from the data, but would definitely be something worth exploring in greater capacity. I'd love to see this as a space for emerging academics, especially among postgraduate students. (+1) ● "AustLit sort of does this with research projects that have active researcher engagement to develop specific outcomes from the data, but would definitely be something worth exploring in greater capacity." - Definitely! I think the AustLit projects are a great model that could be built on here. ● It would be very valuable to be able to store documentation but copyright remains an issue if we are thinking about recordings of productions (and this is very different in Australia compared to other countries which create work through ensembles, for example, and provide greater access to material). (+5) ● dunno about cloud. i prefer established server. I find the cloud/s twitchy and unreliable. But Im a bit of a Luddite. I myself still think we need an institution or institutions with servers and staff. Australia is starved of these, and it's getting worse. Maybe leverage this project to reverse that

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Issues with cloud. Where does the cloud live, who pays for it, national sovereign data questions. (+2) ● Remember US Gov is allowed to access any info on a server in the US. This can be a problem in some cases. Eg: I could not store a collaboration with a refugee because he'd been targeted by US Gov. Also, it's a national defence risk, etc - like when Aus couldn't access it's petrol reserves in Covid because we paid USA to 'host' them. One point of AARNET use to be to preserve integrity of the network in event of disaster. (+1) ● Environmental offsets factored into use of cloud. environmental sustainability can be helpful in guiding design and structure of future infrastructure (+1) ● sustainability is such a big thing with cloud solutions - well, any digital storage solutions (+2) ● Work in collaboration with existing web archives and/or using standard web archiving tools (+2) ● Cloud services would only be useful if they still enabled local management of specific databases ● Video hosting is a dream here - would be wonderful. There is much out of copyright or open access material that could be curated. ● One consideration with cloud-hosting / with any large online dataset, is environmental sustainability, and the energy that it takes to maintain servers which store large amounts of data. ● On expansion & the pull to expand: What is it you should NOT capture and why? ● Preservation issues: Digital preservation coalition: https://www.dpconline.org/ ● Okay, but all the concerns on earlier boards still apply. Who owns this and how and it it protected and why does a cloud database need to swallow everything and constantly expand, like some kind of Borgesian library? A good question might be: what are the benefits of setting sensible and feasible limits on what constitutes a workable data library and why might limits be good for everyone? ● Align with digital preservation work, eg AusEaaSI (+3)

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hmm. What is the National Archives office for if not for this kind of thing? Would not like a 'cloud' to be owned by an international commercial enterprise. ● Ensure data protections are in place (+1) ● True, but the current training data practices of these hyperscale organisations leave a lot to be desired and regulatory protections for data shared with cloud providers may be inadequate ● How would 'our' cloud hosting interact with other collections? ● But then again how can we afford to sustain computing infrastructure for our own purposes? ● environmental sustainability can be helpful in guiding design and structure of future infrastructure ● See HuNI https://huni.net.au/#/search
(other responses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● With end users adding content (or annotating), we have a lot of requests for this, from a good place of not wanting anyone/anyone's work to remain invisible. One thing has come up is need to expand how we may 'validate' history – category that is validated through community memory, where we cannot or cannot any longer access a lot of archival content to confirm, as well as category that is confirmed in conventional academic referenced modes. Another is need to curate, so content created by arts and media makers who identify is not swamped by content create by allies, by 'about us without us' practitioners, etc. Another is ethics, trauma, etc. There is a truth telling agenda which is important. ● There is, though, inherent ethical questions when naming specific individuals (whether living or deceased) as distinct orgs or govt. There is also, if no individual names, trauma when recounting things like insitutionalisation, sterilisation, etc. So there its back to 'charter' etc how to deal with that. Is there to be 'ethics' for the RDC overall, to deal with any insertion or annotation were a truth telling agenda names names or recounts traumatic histories? ● There's a lot to say about engaging with content, i.e. artists in residence working with the archive materials/researchers in

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>residence working with it - that's probably offline convo (we've talked about that with work we're doing but there's others my group here and we're all in different break out rooms)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The same for cloud - these questions are quite similar to constructing the archives themselves, but conscious the different members my group who're tackling the different parts are in different break outs